

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 883075.

METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and
Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D6.1

Survey and State of the Art about possible social sources

Editor(s):	Mpampis Chatzimallis
Responsible Partner:	ViLabs
Status-Version:	Revised Version – 2.0
Date:	15/07/2022
Distribution level (CO, PU):	Public

Copyright message

© METICOS Consortium, 2020- 2023

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Project Number:	GA 883075
Project Title:	METICOS

Title of Deliverable:	Deliverable D6.1: Survey and State of the Art about possible social sources
Due Date of Delivery to the EC:	15/07/2022

Work package responsible for the Deliverable:	WP6 – METICOS Social Toolkit, workshops and recommendations on how to improve the perception of the EU abroad
Editor(s):	Mpampis Chatzimallis, ViLabs
Contributor(s):	NTNU, EUC and All partners
Reviewer(s):	NTNU, EUC and All partners
Approved by:	WP2 & WP6 leaders and All partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	WP5, WP6, WP7 and all WPs
Abstract:	Deliverable D6.1 provides state-of-the-art functional and operational requirements for the METICOS Social Sensing Platform, including methodologies for the description and structuring of the METICOS Platform as well as the requirements for social sensing sources and agent-based simulation tools that will be used. Beyond discussing the foundations of social sensing itself, a broader, user-centric perspective is given by providing an overview of relevant social sensing applications related to interaction with border control technologies. Furthermore, state of the art in METICOS agent-based simulation context (application domain and agent-based simulation tools) is being discussed.
Keyword List:	Technology acceptance, Social sensing, social sensing toolkit
Disclaimer	This deliverable reflects only the author’s views and views and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

Document Description

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	10/03/2021	Table of contents	ViLabs
v0.2	13/06/2021	First version	ViLabs, NTNU
V0.3	29/06/2021	Comments and suggestions received by WP Leader	ViLabs, NTNU
V0.4	14/07/2021	Pre-final version for WP Leader	ViLabs, NTNU, EUC
V0.5	10/08/2021	Pre-final version for project-internal review	All partners
V0.6	20/08/2021	Minor revisions	ViLabs
V1.0	31/08/2021	Final version ready for submission	ViLabs, NTNU, EUC and all partners
V2.0	15/07/2022	Revised document according to the suggestions received during the mid-term review meeting with the European Commission.	ViLabs and all partners

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	6
2	Introduction	7
2.1	Main purpose and objectives	7
2.2	Document Outline	8
3	Background and state-of-the-art	9
3.1	An overview of Smart Border Control Technologies (SBCTs)	9
3.2	Existing Smart Border Control technologies/systems	11
3.2.1	Systems providing services	11
3.3	Agent-based modelling and simulation	15
3.3.1	An overview	15
3.3.2	Benefits of ABMs	17
3.3.3	The application domain of the Agent-based Modelling (ABMS)	17
3.3.4	Tools for designing agent-based simulation	21
3.4	Social sensing	26
3.4.1	An overview of “Sensing”	26
3.4.2	Types of sensing and use	26
3.4.3	Social sensing	28
3.4.4	Social sensing media sources	29
3.4.5	The domain of Social Sensing	30
3.4.6	Technology Enablers of social sensing	33
3.5	Technology acceptance	34
3.5.1	Technology acceptance for border control technologies	35
4	Functional and operational requirements	37
4.1	Social Sensing Toolkit	37
4.2	Identification of required data categories and data types	38
4.2.1	Data categories template	40
4.3	Requirements for social sensing source	42
4.4	Requirements of the agent-based simulation tool	42
4.5	Identification of social sensing techniques to be used for the social sensing toolkit	44
5	Challenges and open issues	47
5.1	Privacy and data protection challenges for social sensing toolkit	47
5.2	Privacy and data protection	47
6	Conclusions and Implications for the METICOS Project	49

7 Bibliography 51
Appendix: Links to information on different existing border control technologies 56

Terms and abbreviations

CO	Confidential
PU	Public
EU	European Union
SoTA	State Of The Art
BCPs	Border Control Points
SBCTs	Smart Border Control technologies
PKD	Public Key Directory
SSTs	Self-Service Technologies
ABC	Automated Border Control
AI	Artificial Intelligence
IoT	Internet of Things
SM	Social Media
ABM	Agent-Based Modelling
ABMS	Agent-Based Modeling & Simulation
M&S	Modelling and Simulation
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering & Mathematics
EM	Electromagnetic
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
BSP	Border Signal Processing
APIs	Application Programming Interfaces
SNS	Social Networking Sites
OSN	Online Social Networks
AOR	Agent Object Relationship
AORL	Agent Object Relationship Language
FAR	False Acceptance Rate
FRR	False Rejection Rate

1 Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.1 provides state-of-the-art functional and operational requirements for the METICOS Social Sensing Platform, including methodologies for the description and structuring of the METICOS Platform as well as the requirements for social sensing sources and agent-based simulation tools that will be used. Beyond discussing the foundations of social sensing itself, a broader, user-centric perspective is given by providing an overview of relevant social sensing applications related to interaction with border control technologies. Furthermore, state of the art in METICOS agent-based simulation context (application domain and agent-based simulation tools) is being discussed.

The current deliverable report consists of six sections: Section 1 provides an executive summary, and Section 2 presents an introduction including the primary purposes, objectives and document outline. Section 3 provides a more general overview of the smart border control technologies (SBCTs) as well as a SOTA review in agent-based simulation (application domain and tools) and social sensing (applications, social sensing media sources). Also, this section includes an overview of technology acceptance, highlighting the relation between technology acceptance and border control technologies. Section 4 then focuses on the functional and operational requirements of the social sensing toolkit, which is the key topic and activity of the D6.1, including: 1) the proposed architecture for developing the METICOS social sensing toolkit, 2) the data collection template, 3) the requirements for social sensing source and agent-based simulation tool and 4) the social sensing techniques that will be used for the social sensing toolkit. Section 5 focuses on challenges and open issues. Finally, in Section 6, a number of conclusions and findings from the surveyed SOTA is derived, particularly as regards upcoming activities in work packages WP5, WP7 and WP8. Among those, key findings and recommendations are:

- A number of Smart Border Control technologies in different countries (including the consortium countries) can improve border crossing process in terms of speed, cost, security, automation, false rejection reduction and many other factors. METICOS project will address two main challenges: i) the need for more effective and efficient Smart Borders and ii) the need for gaining the travellers' acceptance and satisfaction with the use of Smart Borders technologies.
- The integration of AnyLogic, which is an agent-based simulation tool in social sensing platforms, represents a significant research opportunity for the METICOS project. AnyLogic is currently the most appropriate M&S tool for modelling in a modular, hierarchical, and incremental way, allowing systems to be represented to any level of detail.
- According to the requirements for the social sensing source, Twitter is most appropriate for data collection and data processing due to its strong hashtag culture, which makes it easier for gathering, sorting, and extending searches. Specifically, it will help METICOS project to achieve a fuller understanding of the user's/traveller's acceptance of BCPs.

Due to the lack of bibliographical references about the implementation of social sensing at border control technologies, D6.1 will be used as a guide for the following tasks of WP6, D.6.2. "Social Data analysis and extracted perceptions" and D6.3. "METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit".

2 Introduction

2.1 Main purpose and objectives

METICOS aims to introduce Big Data Analysis of border control information systems, in order to provide a step-change towards more modern and efficient Smart Border management and towards gaining societal and political acceptance of modern control technologies of EU borders such as “no gate solutions”. It is therefore positioned as an initiative to create a real-time decision-support system with regard to different Smart Border control technologies in order to ensure user acceptance, secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency. To this end, the METICOS project will develop a platform that integrates information systems and networks of data sources in order to validate the efficiency and users acceptance of border control technologies.

Deliverable D6.1 provides a survey and state of the art (SOTA) possible social sources used for the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit. Specifically, T6.1 is mainly related to such activities as collecting and analysing functional and operational requirements as well as the structuring of METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit. Beyond discussing the foundations of social sensing and agent-based modelling itself, the current deliverable describes how the social sensing toolkit in combination with agent-based simulation will map, analyse and predict individual behaviour of non-EU travellers when faced with new (Border Control Points) BCP technologies.

In this context, this report’s main objectives are:

- To present an overview about border control technologies, providing a list of existing border control technologies;
- To describe the relationship between technology acceptance and border control technologies;
- To explain the field of agent-based modelling & simulation, its’ application domain and the relation to the social sensing toolkit;
- To present an overview of sensing, its types, uses and practices focusing on “social sensing”;
- To discuss the use of social sensing and agent-based modelling in METICOS project in order to understand user’s (border guards and traveller) acceptance;
- To identify required data categories and data types for the METICOS Social Sensing Platform that will be used during D6.2 and D6.3;
- To analyse data collection template for social sensing toolkit; and
- To discuss tools for designing agent-based simulation engine and social sensing techniques that will be used for METICOS Social Sensing Platform.

This survey and SoTA review on possible social sources establish partners responsibilities and timelines, guidelines and suggestions for setting requirements of the social sensing toolkit under the continuous monitoring of the WP6.

To achieve the main objectives of Task 6.1 and D6.1, Figure 1 presents the main steps used to conduct the review.

1. Acquire knowledge: In this step, we conducted a theoretical study in order to gain a comprehensive understanding for: 1) automatic border control (ABC) technologies, 2) technology acceptance for ABC technologies, 3) agent-based modelling and simulations and 4) social sensing. Books, scientific papers (e.g., conferences, journals and technical reports), strategy reports and policy documents served as various sources of knowledge.

2. Requirements collection: in this step, we conduct a state-of-the-art (SOTA) review for: 1) identification of required data categories and data types, 2) identification of required online social networks (OSNs) and 3) tools for designing agent-based simulation engines.
3. Integration into T6.2 and T6.3, in this step, we plan to provide knowledge and requirements collection in order to define and design technical scope for T6.2 and T6.3.
4. Evaluation: in this step, we evaluate the proposed model against the requirements and acquired knowledge into T6.2 and T6.3 for enhancements.

Figure 1: Overview of D6.1 and mapping with other WP6 tasks

2.2 Document Outline

The document is structured into the following 6 sections: Section 1 provides an executive summary of D6.1. Section 2 presents an introduction including the primary purposes and objectives of this deliverable (2.1) and a document outline (2.2). Section 3 (Background) provides an overview of border control technologies with a list of existing smart border control technologies/systems in the different countries (section 3.1 and 3.2). In addition, it explains the field of agent-based modelling & simulation, its benefits, application domain, and tools (section 3.3). Moreover, it provides an overview of “sensing”, its types, focusing on “social sensing”. Also, it describes social sensing media sources and the domain of social sensing (section 3.4). Ending, the next section (3.5) provides an overview of technology acceptance and its relation with border control technologies. Section 4 focuses on the functional and operational requirements for the METICOS Social Sensing Platform. Firstly, it provides the proposed architecture for developing the METICOS social sensing toolkit (4.1) after identification of required data categories and data types for the social sensing toolkit (4.2), followed by a data collection template (4.2.1). Furthermore, requirements for social sensing source (4.3) and agent-based simulation tool (4.4) are analysed, followed by social sensing techniques that will be used for the social sensing toolkit (4.5). Section 5 presents privacy and data protection issues of using smart border technologies. Section 6 offers a summary of the main ideas and the finding of our research.

3 Background and state-of-the-art

This section provides a more general overview of the smart border control technologies (SBCTs) as well as a SOTA in-based simulation (application domain and tools) and social sensing (applications, social sensing media sources). Also, this section includes an overview of technology acceptance, highlighting the relation between technology acceptance and border control technologies.

3.1 An overview of Smart Border Control Technologies (SBCTs)

According to the Schengen Borders Code (SBC - [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/399](#)), border control consists of border checks carried out at border crossing points and of border surveillance, which is carried out between border crossing points in order to prevent people from circumventing border checks. When crossing external borders, third-country nationals are subject to thorough checks, including verification of identity and nationality, and systematic consultation of relevant databases such as the SIS, the VIS (including fingerprint verification, where applicable), and Interpol's database on stolen and lost travel documents (SLDT).¹

In the last years, border management has been for a long time going through significant transformation, leading to the movement towards a more modern and efficient border management approach following for the needs of the Schengen Area.²

The “Smart Borders” Package was proposed by the Commission in February 2013. It follows the European Commission (EC) Communication of February 2008 suggesting the establishment of an [Entry/Exit System](#) (EES) and a [Registered Traveller Programme](#) (RTP)³.

*“It aims to improve the management of the external borders of the Schengen Member States, fight against irregular immigration and provide information on overstayers, as well as facilitate border crossings for pre-vetted frequent third country national (TCN) travellers”.*⁴

Nowadays, the world is facing an unprecedented global health, social and economic emergency as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic had a negative impact on world scheduled passenger traffic for the year 2020, compared to 2019 levels⁵. Specifically, it was observed for air traffic: 1) an overall reduction of air passengers (both international and domestic) ranging from 60% in 2020 compared to 2019, 2) An estimated loss of approximately 64.6% of passenger traffic and 66.3% or over USD 125 billion airport revenues in 2020 compared to business as usual and 3) A 65.9% decline of revenue passenger kilometres (RPKs, both international and domestic) in 2020 compared to 2019⁶. Same was the situation also for the passengers embarking and disembarking in EU ports. Maritime

¹ Second edition. The 'EU Legislation in Progress' briefings are updated at key stages throughout the legislative procedure. (2022). Retrieved 8 July 2022, from [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/659346/EPRS_BRI\(2020\)659346_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/659346/EPRS_BRI(2020)659346_EN.pdf)

² European Agency for the operational management of large-scale IT systems in the area of freedom, security and justice. (2015). *Smart Borders Pilot Project Report on the technical conclusions of the Pilot Volume 1* (p. 5). Brussels.

³ Smart borders - background. (2022). Retrieved 7 July 2022, from https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/pages/page/smart-borders-background_en

⁴ Smart borders - background. (2022). Retrieved 4 July 2022, from https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/pages/page/smart-borders-background_en

⁵ https://www.icao.int/sustainability/Documents/Covid-19/ICAO_coronavirus_Econ_Impact.pdf

⁶ https://www.icao.int/sustainability/Documents/Covid-19/ICAO_coronavirus_Econ_Impact.pdf

transport of passengers in EU ports was severely hit by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, some 230 million passengers passed through ports in the European Union, when in 2019 the number was around 400 millions.⁷ The latter corresponds to a decrease of 45% compared to 2019.⁸ In terms of land traffic, according to the International Road Transport Union⁹, the international coach transport and national passenger transports markets have been worst effected, with “*Tourist services halted and interurban services fell to almost half normal levels*”.¹⁰

However, in 2021, worldwide traffic has an upward trend due to the COVID-19 vaccine; border control have been maintained, with a similar workforce having a substantially higher workload. Increasing passenger numbers also imply increased security and safety risks. With a higher passenger throughput, it will be more challenging to satisfy customers' (travellers) high service standards. Thus, the adoption of innovative technologies is a valuable approach to accommodate future increases in passenger traffic while maintaining high standards of security, safety, and service.

“Smart Border control technologies (SBCTs)” are defined as technologies that allow travellers to cross borders without being slowed down by physical checks and are based on automated risk assessment and/or biometric verification processes. While the use of biometric technologies appears to be a promising path toward achieving a seamless border crossing experience for the majority of travellers, the often-overlooked potential impact of its deployment has yet to be fully understood. Thus, the challenges related to the development of biometric technologies extend beyond improved recognition accuracy. This method will most likely include SoTA technologies in the form of an information system and a network of sensors capable of detecting, recording, processing, and storing data that would otherwise have to be gathered through more time-consuming methods.

An example of such technologies is the **E-passport gates**, which are border-controlled automated self-service barriers located at checkpoints in several European airports (Figure 2). End-users must operate these self-service checkpoints/technologies with no intermediary. While border agents and border management regard e-passport gates as a safe and convenient alternative to traditional border checking and crossing, not all travellers choose to use these new self-service technologies (SSTs). Passengers are unable or unwilling to use self-service systems for a variety of reasons such as: 1) lack of awareness, 2) difficulty in use, 3) privacy and data protection concerns, 4) lack of technological background, 5) low educational background, 5) different cultures, 6) gate design, 7) passenger's age, 8) gender, 9) nationality and such¹¹.

⁷ Number of passengers embarking and disembarking in European Union's (EU-27) in 2020, by Country. (2021). Retrieved 23 June 2022, from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/MAR_MP_AA_CPH_custom_2969087/bookmark/table?lang=en&bookmarkId=7c9f2402-494c-4969-a3d2-4b7ad8f025c4

⁸ Maritime passenger statistics - Statistics Explained. (2021). Retrieved 1 July 2022, from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Maritime_passenger_statistics&oldid=550549

⁹ <https://www.iru.org/news-resources/newsroom/covid-19-urgent-eu-action-needed-road-borders-drivers-and-financial-support>

¹⁰ Debyser, A. (2020). Mobility, transport and coronavirus Briefing Report. Retrieved 1 July 2022, from [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/651908/EPRS_BRI\(2020\)651908_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/651908/EPRS_BRI(2020)651908_EN.pdf)

¹¹ M. Ylikauppila, S. Toivonen, M. Kulju, and M. Jokela, “Understanding the factors affecting UX and technology acceptance in the context of automated border controls,” in 2014 IEEE Joint Intelligence and Security Informatics Conference, 2014, pp. 168–175.

The automated border crossing process includes three types of checks: 1) travel document authentication, 2) biometric verification of the traveller’s identity, and 3) travellers legal restrictions/permissions to cross the borders. The Automated Border Control (ABC) method initially checks that the passenger is in possession of a genuine and valid passport. Following that, it live-captures a biometric sample—typically a face image, fingerprint, or iris image—for a one-to-one match with the image received from the biometric document holder. Finally, it checks that the traveller has the legal right to cross the border. An officer in a remote station supervises the ABC system and can intervene if problems arise. Automated biometric gates, also known as e-Gates, automatically verify the traveller's identity, allowing their passage in the case of success. Regular e-Gates use an electronic machine-readable travel document (e-MRTD), which is typically an e-Passport that complies with ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization) specifications and contains biometric samples of the owner.

Figure 2 METICOS project architecture for the management of border control points and a typical Automated Border Control e-gate¹²

3.2 Existing Smart Border Control technologies/systems

3.2.1 Systems providing services

BorderXpress Technology allows travellers to complete the administrative requirements of border control by using biometric-enabled kiosks as part of an efficient two-step process¹³. Specifically, the

¹² “Australia to introduce next generation Automated Border Control eGates,” [PASSENGER SELF SERVICE, Jul. 27, 2017.](https://www.passengerselfservice.com/2017/07/australia-to-introduce-next-generation-automated-border-control-egates/) <https://www.passengerselfservice.com/2017/07/australia-to-introduce-next-generation-automated-border-control-egates/> (accessed Aug. 02, 2021).

¹³ “BorderXpress™ – Innovative Travel Solutions.” <https://www.innovativetravelsolutions.ca/products/borderxpress/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

information is sent, fully encrypted with data protection to a border agency allowing the traveller's identity to be verified in real-time. After receiving a token, the traveller is directed to a border officer or an e-gate to complete the journey into or out of the country. BorderXpress Technology is designed to enhance the security and safety of the border by complementing the expertise of the border guards¹⁴.

EasyPass is an automated border control system designed firstly for third-country nationals when entering Germany¹⁵. Specifically, EasyPASS uses eGates as a quick and convenient alternative to traditional border controls. Recently EasyPASS became available to U.S citizens. By using EasyPASS, travellers can quickly accomplish border control on their own. The travellers must only scan their electronic travel documents and look into the camera in order to be through border crossing¹⁶. The automated border control system has a number of advantages, including the fact that it is extremely secure, simple to use and speeds up border crossings¹⁷. Also, this procedure may be very useful for frequent travellers as a simple, quick, and easy alternative as the border checks are largely automated.

The BKC-KORDON system is intended to control the flow of passengers and vehicles crossing the state border and can be applied to automobile, air, sea and pedestrian crossing points¹⁸. Specifically, CONDOR is a full-page document reader with a built-in computer for passport control: 1) Automatic reading and checking of documents in 3 seconds, 2) Validation of passports, ID-cards, driver's licenses, visas and other documents, including RFID-based contactless identification circuits (RFID), 3) Check listings (Stop List) and databases using on-line services and 4) Recognition of text information¹⁹.

Smart Tunnel Technology, by the use of facial recognition, allows travellers to complete the passport control procedure within 15 seconds and without the need for human intervention²⁰. Passengers must show their passports and IDs at check-in; however, they can complete their passport control without the need of them until they reach the gates. So, smart tunnel technology can improve the conditions of the entire journey in terms of speed as it will be like a walk-through²¹.

Aruba Happy Flow, which has been implemented in Aruba Airport, is a new experience for travellers that allows for a touchless, streamlined airport journey²². Travel documents are only required at check-in while the passenger's identity is checked, and a virtual identity is created. Following check-in, the passenger goes through baggage drop-off, pass security access, border control, and facial recognition

¹⁴ "BorderXpress™ – Innovative Travel Solutions." <https://www.innovativetravelsolutions.ca/products/borderxpress/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

¹⁵ "EasyPASS - EasyPASS-RTP." https://www.easypass.de/EasyPass/EN/EasyPASS-RTP/rtp_node.html (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

¹⁶ "EasyPASS," *U.S. Customs and Border Protection*. <https://www.cbp.gov/global-entry/other-programs/easypass> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

¹⁷ "EasyPASS - EasyPASS-RTP." https://www.easypass.de/EasyPass/EN/EasyPASS-RTP/rtp_node.html (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

¹⁸ "Bancomzvjazok." <https://www.bkc.com.ua/en/direction-cordon/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

¹⁹ "Bancomzvjazok." <https://www.bkc.com.ua/en/direction-cordon/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

²⁰ "Video: Just walk through a tunnel for Dubai Airports passport control | Transport – Gulf News." <https://gulfnews.com/uae/transport/video-just-walk-through-a-tunnel-for-dubai-airports-passport-control-1.69728701> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

²¹ "Video: Just walk through a tunnel for Dubai Airports passport control | Transport – Gulf News." <https://gulfnews.com/uae/transport/video-just-walk-through-a-tunnel-for-dubai-airports-passport-control-1.69728701> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

²² "Aruba Happy Flow lays foundations for European preclearance," *Future Travel Experience*, Jun. 04, 2015. <https://www.futuretravelexperience.com/2015/06/aruba-happy-flow-lays-foundations-for-european-precleanance/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

to board the plane without having to show any travel document²³. User-centric self-service Passenger TouchPoints (Self-service Baggage Drop stations, Automated Security Access, Border Control eGates and self-Boarding Gates) identify each passenger's face and compare it to a fully secured database, allowing only authorized passengers to proceed.

Authorities benefit from Aruba Happy Flow as well: an end-to-end passenger flow orchestration platform connecting all passenger touchpoints ensures a real-time overview of passengers' individual clearance processes, and efficient monitoring of passenger flow, centralized control and optimization of the entire security infrastructure²⁴. Furthermore, Aruba Happy Flow is safe, fast and straightforward and is designed in line with EU GDPR standards in order to ensure the privacy of all passengers in a strict and uniform manner while making no compromises in terms of safety.

Below one can find an indicative table (Table 1) of representative countries (countries representing partners of the METICOS consortium as well as other countries where other studies have focused upon, in correlation with the different types of Border Crossing points (air, land and maritime) as well as the technologies which have been mentioned at previous subsection and their functionalities.

All the information about existing border control technologies in different countries was found after a thorough search in sites related to SBCTs and related functionalities for every country, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Smart Border Control Points

Country	SBCP	Functionalities/System	Information
Cyprus	Larnaca & Paphos International Airport	Biometric identification technology (BorderXpress)	Appendix A.1
Estonia	Tallinn airport (air) & Narva road border crossing (land)[1]	Biometric passport (e-passport), (AS Alarmtec), (GoSwift System) (secunet)	Appendix A.2
Greece	Athens International Airport (air) & Kipoi Evrou (land)	Biometric identification technology	Appendix A.3
Romania	The Bucharest Airports Company (CNAB)	Biometric Identification technology (BKC-KORDON system)	Appendix A.4
Ukraine	Ukraine's Boryspil International Airport	Biometric passport (e-passport)	Appendix A.5
Israel	Ben Gurion Airport	Biometric identification technology	Appendix A.6

²³ "Vision-Box's Happy Flow™ Inaugurated at Aruba Airport | Vision-Box is the leading provider of electronic identity management solutions, improving efficiency and security in gov, travel, border control and more." <https://www.vision-box.com/pressroom/press-releases/vision-boxs-happy-flow-inaugurated-at-aruba-airport> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

²⁴ "Aruba Happy Flow lays foundations for European preclearance," *Future Travel Experience*, Jun. 04, 2015. <https://www.futuretravelexperience.com/2015/06/aruba-happy-flow-lays-foundations-for-european-precleanance/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).

Aruba	Aruba International Airport	Biometric identification technology (Happy Flow)	Appendix A.7
Australia	Adelaide, Brisbane, Cairns, Canberra, Gold Coast, Darwin, Melbourne, Perth and Sydney	All e-gate self-services	Appendix A.8
China	Beijing Capital International Airport (PEK), Shanghai Hongqiao International Airport (SHA)	Facial recognition technology	Appendix A.9
Dubai	Dubai International (DXB) Airport	Facial and Iris recognition technology Using machine learning and artificial intelligence	Appendix A.10
Germany	All Airports	Passport Scanner Biometric Verification (EasyPass)	Appendix A.11
Paris, France	Charles de Gaulle Airport, Orly Airport and Le Bourget Airport	Facial authentication, Fingerprint authentication (PARAFE system)	Appendix A.12
Portugal	Portugal Airport	Facial recognition (RAPID system)	Appendix A.13
Qatar	Hamad International Airport (HIA)	Biometric identification technology	Appendix A.14
United Kingdom (UK)	Heathrow International Airport	Facial recognition technology	Appendix A.15
Spain	Six International airports, Valencia, Fuerteventure, Bilbao	More than 120 ABC Gates	Appendix A.16
Norway	Oslo Gardermoen Airport	Automatic passport verification and facial recognition technology	Appendix A.17
Hungary	Udvar (roal/land border)	ABC Gates (secunet)	Appendix A.18
Italy	Genoa (port/sea)	Fingerprint scanner (secunet)	Appendix A.19

Slovenia	Obrezje (land)	Easykiosks (secunet)	Appendix A.20
Ukraine	Over 200 crossing points of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine (land)	Border control Gart-1/P Automated “Inspector-K”	Appendix A.21

The previous table presents a number of Smart Border Control technologies in different countries (including the consortium countries) and different systems/providers such as “smart tunnel”, “biometric terminal”, “borderXpress technology”, “Happy Flow”, “EasyPass”, “RAPID system” etc. The technologies of consortium countries are envisaged to be taken into account by the METICOS platform during the pilots. During the project lifetime, there may be changes in the number of pilots being envisaged, the countries where these pilots are likely to happen, the description of the pilots, and the technologies envisaged being monitored.

In terms of the Areas that METICOS is going to be piloted and tested these are the following:

- a) Estonia: The pilot activities will take place in Tallinn Old City harbour B terminal (sea). The equipment that will be used is the following: document reader/scanner, the DERMALOG fingerprint reader/scanner and document control equipment.
- b) Cyprus: The pilot activities will take place in the Larnaka airport (air). The equipment to be validated is: the Interactive borderXpress kiosks and an integrated passport reader (MRZ).
- c) Greece: The pilot will take place in the Border Control Point of Kipoi (land) or at the Eleftherios Venizelos Athens International airport. As for the equipment to be used, this will be a mobile fingerprint scanner, Smart Borders (ABC) and passport scanner.
- d) Romania: The pilot activities will take place in the border control point of Moravita Timisoara, while the equipment to be used/validated is still to be decided.
- e) Ending, the project is exploring the possibility of additional, to the initial DoA, pilot activities to take place in other European countries (such as Austria). Additional information will be shared on the corresponding Deliverable reports, as this is not the purpose of the current document.

In case of alternations, these will be analysed in the upcoming corresponding deliverables of the project. The following section includes agent-based modelling and simulation.

3.3 Agent-based modelling and simulation

3.3.1 An overview

Simulation tools are increasingly being used in various research topics in the social and behavioural sciences to map and predict outcomes that would otherwise be difficult to achieve across a wide range of situations. In this context, simulation is primarily seen as a feasible method for visualizing or validating specific theories after performing a large number of runs with sets of predefined values matching as possible real-world cases.

Agent-based modelling (ABM) includes systems that are modelled as a collection of autonomous decision-making entities called agents. Each agent evaluates its situation independently and makes decisions based on a set of rules. Agents can execute various behaviours that are appropriate for the system they represent, such as producing, consuming, or selling. Agent-based modelling, which relies on the power of computers to study dynamics beyond the reach of pure mathematical methods, includes repetitive competitive interactions between agents²⁵. An agent-based model, at its simplest level, consists of a set of agents and the interactions between them (Figure 3). Even a simple agent-based model can display complex behaviour patterns²⁶ and provide helpful information about the dynamics of the real-world system it mimics. Agents may also be capable of evolving, allowing unexpected behaviours to arise²⁷.

A typical agent-based model contains three main elements:

- *Agents*, encompassing a possibly heterogeneous behavioural specification.
- An *environment*, supplying agents with their perceptions and enabling their actions.
- *Rules* governing each agent’s behaviour and its local interactions with other agents and with the environment.

Figure 3 An abstract model to analyze, describe and discuss different models, concrete simulation experiences, platforms legitimately claiming to adopt an agent-based approach²⁸

²⁵ R. Axelrod, *The complexity of cooperation: Agent-based models of competition and collaboration*, vol. 3. Princeton university press, 1997.

²⁶ C. W. Reynolds, “Flocks, herds and schools: A distributed behavioral model,” in *Proceedings of the 14th annual conference on Computer graphics and interactive techniques*, 1987, pp. 25–34.

²⁷ E. Bonabeau, “Agent-based modeling: Methods and techniques for simulating human systems,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 99, no. suppl 3, pp. 7280–7287, 2002.

²⁸ M. Herrera, M. Pérez-Hernández, A. Kumar Parlikad, and J. Izquierdo, “Multi-agent systems and complex networks: Review and applications in systems engineering,” *Processes*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 312, 2020.

3.3.2 Benefits of ABMs

ABMS provides a number of advantages compared to other modelling techniques. To begin with, it has the ability to capture emergent phenomena²⁹; which are behaviours not explicitly specified in a micro-level decision or behavioural rules that emerge at the macro-level. Secondly, ABMS provides an environment in which naturally occurring systems can be studied³⁰. For example, modelling how people move around a city is a more natural approach to modelling crowd behaviour than using simultaneous equations to represent crowd behaviour. Thirdly, ABMS is flexible³¹, as the number of agents and their behaviours can be easily changed, which is important for conducting simulation experiments.

For all the reasons mentioned above, ABMS was chosen for the METICOS project. Furthermore, an advantage of using ABMS in the project is that with simulation, travellers' behaviour can be predicted, while due to some ethical challenges, there isn't the possibility to try everything to the pilots.

3.3.3 The application domain of the Agent-based Modelling (ABMS)

Agent-based modelling is being applied to many areas, spanning human social, physical and biological systems. Some application domains of ABMS and their model description are listed in Table 2, with an exemplar publication for each domain. All of the cited publications make a case for agent-based modelling as the preferred modelling approach versus other modelling techniques for the particular application domain, and the identified challenges. Some studies in which ABMS is used, are analyzed below.

ABMS has been widely used in higher education to explore academic activities. Caillou and Sebag³² implemented an ABMS application to investigate how universities recruit the best employee candidates with high confidence. The simulations indicate that 'top' and 'medium' rated universities have no difficulty recruiting the talent they have selected, while 'low-ranked' universities are likely to struggle to secure the recruitment of acceptable candidates. In contrast, Zheng and Lei³³ used ABMS to study talent management to resolve issues relating to knowledge innovation and academic impact in universities, demonstrating that a knowledge innovation-oriented stance in managing talent leads to better systematic efficiency.

In the paper of D. Grether, S. Fürbas, and K. Nagel, "Agent-based modelling and simulation of air transport technology"³⁴, a microscopic modelling approach for air transport technology is proposed. A multi-agent simulation approach from urban transport planning was used. Aircraft were represented

²⁹ E. Bonabeau, "Agent-based modeling: Methods and techniques for simulating human systems," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 99, no. suppl 3, pp. 7280–7287, 2002.; N. Malleon, "Using agent-based models to simulate crime," in *Agent-based models of geographical systems*, Springer, 2012, pp. 411–434.; R. B. Matthews, N. G. Gilbert, A. Roach, J. G. Polhill, and N. M. Gotts, "Agent-based land-use models: a review of applications," *Landsc. Ecol.*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 1447–1459, 2007.

³⁰ E. Bonabeau, "Agent-based modeling: Methods and techniques for simulating human systems," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 99, no. suppl 3, pp. 7280–7287, 2002.

³¹ E. Bonabeau, "Agent-based modeling: Methods and techniques for simulating human systems," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 99, no. suppl 3, pp. 7280–7287, 2002.

³² P. Caillou and M. Sebag, "Pride and prejudice on a centralized academic labor market," in *Artificial economics*, Springer, 2009, pp. 29–40.

³³ Q. Zheng and S. Lei, "An agent-based experimental model for innovative talent management in universities," in *2010 International Conference on Electronics and Information Engineering*, 2010, vol. 1, pp. V1-552-V1-556.

³⁴ D. Grether, S. Fürbas, and K. Nagel, "Agent-based modelling and simulation of air transport technology," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 19, pp. 821–828, 2013.

microscopically, featuring attributes as speed, available seats and boarding constraints. The air traffic network and flight performance were modelled at a low level of detail as the model is not intended for air traffic management. Despite the lack of detail, some relevant aspects of congestion and delays can be captured by the use of a queuing model for traffic flow. The results showed that the proposed approach could be used to model some important characteristics of air traffic technology, such as runway capacity restrictions.

The paper “Using an agent-based simulation for predicting the effects of patients derivation policies in emergency departments,”³⁵ presents the results of an experiment in the domain of Healthcare which was carried out with the objective of analyzing the effects (patients’ Length of Stay, the number of patients attended and the level of activity of ED Staff) of different derivation policies on the hospital ED (emergency departments). The experiment has been done with data of the Hospital of Sabadell (a big hospital, one of the most important in Catalonia, Spain), making use of an Agent-Based Model and simulation formed entirely of the rules governing the behaviour of the individual agents which populate the ED, and due to the great amount of data that should be computed, using High-Performance Computing. The experiment presented in the paper is a clear example of the benefits of using simulation as the core component of a decision support system that aids healthcare managers to make the best-informed decisions possible (patient admission scheduling, managing physician staff and resource optimization, amongst other situations), and making better use of resources, achieving a more efficient and improved patient care cycle. This, in turn, allows better management of dynamic patient flow, either as a result of specific circumstances (pandemics, disasters, etc.) or seasonal fluctuation of the demand of healthcare service.

In another study, the “Sub-orbital space tourism: Predictions of the future marketplace using agent-based modelling,”³⁶ agent-based simulation is used in order to model possible futures for a market in sub-orbital space tourism. Each agent represents an entity within the space industry, such as consumers, producers, the government, etc., that provides or demands different products and services.

There are many more agent-based modelling publications in each of the application domain listed in Table 2, and there are many more application areas than the table references to which agent-based modelling is being successfully applied.

Table 2 Application Domain of ABMS

Application Domain	Model Description	Authors	Year
Healthcare	Agent-based modelling and simulation of care delivery for patients with thrombotic and bleeding disorders ³⁷	Giordano, N., Rosati, S., Valeri, F., Borchiellini, A., &	2020

³⁵ M. Taboada, E. Cabrera, F. Epelde, M. L. Iglesias, and E. Luque, “Using an agent-based simulation for predicting the effects of patients derivation policies in emergency departments,” *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 18, pp. 641–650, 2013.

³⁶ A. C. Charania, J. R. Olds, and D. DePasquale, “Sub-orbital space tourism: Predictions of the future marketplace using agent-based modeling,” in *Proceedings of the 57th International Astronautical Congress (AIAA), Valencia, Spain, 2006*, pp. 2–6.

³⁷ N. Giordano, S. Rosati, F. Valeri, A. Borchiellini, and G. Balestra, “Agent-Based Modeling and Simulation of Care Delivery for Patients with Thrombotic and Bleeding Disorders.,” in *MIE*, 2020, pp. 1193–1194.

		Balestra, G	
	Agent-based modelling and simulation of individual elderly care decision-making ³⁸	Lebherz, D. S., Lorig, F., & Timm, I. J.	2019
	Agent-based modelling and simulation of blood vessels in the cardiovascular system ³⁹	Bora, Ş., Evren, V., Emek, S., & Çakırlar, I.	2019
	Multi-Agent Based Modelling and Simulation for Understanding Tempo-Spatial Patterns of Surgery Wait Times ⁴⁰	Li, T., Liang, L., Zili, Z., Hong, L., & Fuyuan, X.	2017
	Agent-based Modelling and Simulation to Adoption Process of Information Technologies in Health Systems ⁴¹	Pardo, M., & Coronado, W. F.	2016
<i>Traffic Management and transport</i>	Agent-based Modelling and Simulation of Tour Planning in Urban Freight Traffic ⁴²	Martins-Turner, K., Nagel, K., & Zilske, M.	2019
	Simulation-Based Evolutionary Optimization of Air Traffic Management ⁴³	Vincent J.L.Gan, H.K.Wong, K.T.Tse, Jack C.P.Cheng, Irene M.C.Lo, C.M.Chan	2020
	Agent-Based Modelling and Simulation of Coordination by Airline Operations Control ⁴⁴	Bouarfa, S., Blom, H. A., & Curran, R.	2016
	Multi-agent-based modelling and simulation of high-speed train ⁴⁵	LiKou, Wenhui Fan, Shuang Song	2020
<i>Smart Energy</i>	Models Within Models - Agent-Based Modelling and Simulation in Energy Systems	Klein, M., Frey, U. J., & Reeg, M.	2019

³⁸ D. S. Lebherz, F. Lorig, and I. J. Timm, "Agent-based modeling and simulation of individual elderly care decision-making," in 2018 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC), 2018, pp. 1025–1036.

³⁹ Ş. Bora, V. Evren, S. Emek, and I. Çakırlar, "Agent-based modeling and simulation of blood vessels in the cardiovascular system," *Simulation*, vol. 95, no. 4, pp. 297–312, 2019.

⁴⁰ T. Li, L. Liang, Z. Zili, L. Hong, and X. Fuyuan, "Multi-Agent Based Modelling and Simulation for Understanding Tempo-Spatial Patterns of Surgery Wait Times," *J. Syst. Simul.*, vol. 29, no. 5, p. 979, 2017.

⁴¹ M. Pardo and W. F. Coronado, "Agent-based modeling and simulation to adoption process of information technologies in health systems," *IEEE Lat. Am. Trans.*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 3358–3363, 2016.

⁴² K. Martins-Turner, K. Nagel, and M. Zilske, "Agent-based modelling and simulation of tour planning in urban freight traffic," 2019.

⁴³ A. Pellegrini et al., "Simulation-Based Evolutionary Optimization of Air Traffic Management," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 161551–161570, 2020. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3021192.

⁴⁴ S. Bouarfa, H. A. Blom, and R. Curran, "Agent-based modeling and simulation of coordination by airline operations control," *IEEE Trans. Emerg. Top. Comput.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 9–20, 2016.

⁴⁵ L. Kou, W. H. Fan, and S. Song, "Multi-agent-based modelling and simulation of high-speed train," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 86, p. 12, 2020. doi: 10.1016/j.compeleceng.2020.106744.

	Analysis ⁴⁶		
	Agent Based Modelling and Simulation of Plug-in Electric Vehicles Adoption in Norway ⁴⁷	Harbo, S. F., Zaferanlouei, S., & Korpås, M.	2018
<i>Supply Chain</i>	Agent-Based Modelling and Simulation of Inter-Organizational Integration and Coordination of Supply Chain Participants ⁴⁸	Sergeyev, V. I., & Lychkina, N. N.	2019
	Agent-Based Modelling and Simulation of Inventory Disruption Management in Supply Chain ⁴⁹	Kessentini, M., Saoud, N. B. B., & Sboui, S.	2018
	Applications of agent-based modelling and simulation in the agri-food supply chains ⁵⁰	Utomo, D. S., Onggo, B. S., & Eldridge, S.	2018
<i>Finance & E-commerce</i>	Agent based modelling and simulation for home financing. Application in netlogo platform ⁵¹	Yachou, N., & Aboulaich, R.	2018
	Agent-based modelling and simulation in the analysis of customer behaviour on B2C e-commerce sites ⁵²	Čavoški, S., & Marković, A.	2017
	Agent-based modelling and simulation for ship unloading processes: Determining the number of trucks and container cranes ⁵³	Ramadhan, F., Imran, A., Rizana, A. F., & Okdinawati, L.	2020
<i>Chemical</i>	Applying agent based modelling and simulation for domino effect assessment in	Zhang, L., Landucci, G., Reniers, G. L. L. M. E., Ovidi, F., Khakzad, N., & Zhou,	2018

⁴⁶ M. Klein, U. J. Frey, and M. Reeg, "Models Within Models–Agent-Based Modelling and Simulation in Energy Systems Analysis," *J. Artif. Soc. Soc. Simul.*, vol. 22, no. 4, 2019.

⁴⁷ S. F. Harbo, S. Zaferanlouei, and M. Korpås, "Agent based modelling and simulation of plug-in electric vehicles adoption in norway," in 2018 Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC), 2018, pp. 1–7.

⁴⁸ V. I. Sergeyev and N. N. Lychkina, "Agent-based modelling and simulation of inter-organizational integration and coordination of supply chain participants," in 2019 IEEE 21st Conference on Business Informatics (CBI), 2019, vol. 1, pp. 436–444.

⁴⁹ M. Kessentini, N. B. B. Saoud, and S. Sboui, "Agent-Based Modeling and Simulation of Inventory Disruption Management in Supply Chain," in 2018 International Conference on High Performance Computing & Simulation (HPCS), 2018, pp. 1008–1014.

⁵⁰ D. S. Utomo, B. S. Onggo, and S. Eldridge, "Applications of agent-based modelling and simulation in the agri-food supply chains," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 269, no. 3, pp. 794–805, 2018.

⁵¹ N. YACHOU and R. Aboulaich, "Agent Based Modeling and Simulation for Home Financing. Application in Netlogo Platform.," *J. Appl. Econ. Sci.*, vol. 13, no. 3, 2018.

⁵² S. Čavoški and A. Marković, "Agent-based modelling and simulation in the analysis of customer behaviour on B2C e-commerce sites," *J. Simul.*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 335–345, 2017.

⁵³ F. Ramadhan, A. Imran, A. F. Rizana, and L. Okdinawati, "Agent-based modelling and simulation for ship unloading processes: determining the number of trucks and container cranes," *Int. J. Simul. Multidiscip. Des. Optim.*, vol. 11, p. 13, 2020.

	the chemical industries ⁵⁴	J.	
<i>Smart Grid</i>	An Agent Based Model for Diffusion of Smart Grid Technology in the Society ⁵⁵	Nasir, S., Asif, M., & Ullah, S.	2018
<i>Architecture & Construction</i>	Agent-based modelling and simulation for food court seating design ⁵⁶	M. El-ghory, O. Tolba, A. El-antabli	2020
	Predicting labor costs in construction projects using agent-based modelling and simulation ⁵⁷	Dabirian, S., Khanzadi, M., & Moussazadeh, M.	2016

Although existing research in the domain of ABC technologies has been limited, previous applications and methodologies of ABMS in other domains can provide input and information for border control technologies. Specifically, the agent-based simulation will be used at METICOS project in order to monitor the social acceptance considering the different behavioural patterns of the travellers and the interactions between them trying to pass the EU border control systems. Furthermore, since the ultimate goal is to evolve to a safe and successful no-gate system, the simulation tool will go towards that goal and provide related outcomes.

3.3.4 Tools for designing agent-based simulation

The technologies that are appropriate for ABMS application have been addressed in a number of review papers⁵⁸ the “Agent Based Modelling and Simulation tools: A review of the state-of-art software,”⁵⁹ the “Agent based modelling and simulation: an informatics perspective,” and⁶⁰, “Agent-based and individual-based modelling: a practical introduction”.

Specifically, the scientific paper “Agent-Based Modelling and Simulation tools: A review of the state-of-art software”⁶¹ presents a comprehensive comparative literature survey of the state-of-art in software agent-based computing technology and its incorporation within the modelling and simulation domain. Comparing the usability features of the toolkits is difficult because each one is unique and has been designed for distinct purposes. Some ABMS packages such as Altreva Adaptive Modeler,

⁵⁴ L. Zhang, G. Landucci, G. Reniers, F. Ovidi, N. Khakzad, and J. Zhou, “Applying agent based modelling and simulation for domino effect assessment in the chemical industries,” *Chem. Eng.*, vol. 67, 2018.

⁵⁵ S. Nasir, M. Asif, and S. Ullah, “An Agent Based Model for Diffusion of Smart Grid Technology in the Society,” in 2018 14th International Conference on Emerging Technologies (ICET), 2018, pp. 1–6.

⁵⁶ M. EL-GOHARY, O. TOLBA, and A. EL-ANTABLI, “AGENT-BASED MODELING AND SIMULATION FOR FOOD COURT SEATING DESIGN,” *J. Eng. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 771–788, 2020.

⁵⁷ S. Dabirian, M. Khanzadi, and M. Moussazadeh, “Predicting labor costs in construction projects using agent-based modeling and simulation,” *Sci. Iran.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 91–101, 2016.

⁵⁸ S. Abar, G. K. Theodoropoulos, P. Lemarinier, and G. M. O’Hare, “Agent Based Modelling and Simulation tools: A review of the state-of-art software,” *Comput. Sci. Rev.*, vol. 24, pp. 13–33, 2017.

⁵⁹ S. Bandini, S. Manzoni, and G. Vizzari, “Agent based modeling and simulation: an informatics perspective,” *J. Artif. Soc. Soc. Simul.*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 4, 2009.

⁶⁰ S. F. Railsback and V. Grimm, *Agent-based and individual-based modeling: a practical introduction*. Princeton university press, 2019.

⁶¹ S. Abar, G. K. Theodoropoulos, P. Lemarinier, and G. M. O’Hare, “Agent Based Modelling and Simulation tools: A review of the state-of-art software,” *Comput. Sci. Rev.*, vol. 24, pp. 13–33, 2017.

AgentSheets, Mathematica® (Wolfram) etc., have built-in support for visual, intuitive graphical user tools that facilitate model development through flexible drag-and-drop interfaces, real-time visualisation via charting and plotting to understand the models' adaptation, evolution, and functional profiles⁶². Almost all the proposed tools are freely available at no cost, open-source and compliant to lenient end-user licensing provisions⁶³. While some shareware offer trial versions, the majority are closed source and have proprietary or restrictive license agreements. Most tools include detailed technical documentation, user manuals, tutorials, and public support mailing lists.

Five modelling and simulation tools have been identified as the most appropriate to support such activities and the agent-based simulation engine for the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit. Below, one can find an informative table (Table 3) containing information and the services/features provided by each of the identified tools:

Table 3 CloudSim, Eve, EcoLab, Cybelpro & AnyLogic ABMS tools

Tool	Info	Domain	Modelling Strength	Development Effort	Language	Supports External Database	Supports Other Languages
Cloudsim	http://www.cloudbus.org/cloudsim/	Specially for modelling of cloud computing	Large Scale	Moderate	Java	No	No
Eve	https://eve.almende.com/	General purpose	Small Scale	Moderate	Java	No	No
Ecolab	http://ecolab.sourceforge.net	General purpose	Large Scale	Complex/Hard	C++	No	No
Cybelpro	http://i-a-i.com/cybelpro	High performance distributed systems	Large Scale	Moderate	Java	No	No
AnyLogic	https://www.anylogic.com/	General purpose Supports Multi-Agents Systems	High/Large Scale	Moderate	Java	No	No

- **CloudSim**

⁶² N. Gilbert and S. Banks, "Platforms and methods for agent-based modeling," Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., vol. 99, no. suppl 3, pp. 7197–7198, 2002.

⁶³ R. Tobias and C. Hofmann, "Evaluation of free Java-libraries for social-scientific agent based simulation," J. Artif. Soc. Soc. Simul., vol. 7, no. 1, p. online, 2004.

CloudSim is a simulation toolkit that enables modelling and simulation of Cloud computing systems and application provisioning environments. Both system and behaviour modelling of Cloud system components such as data centres, virtual machines (VMs), and resource provisioning policies are supported by the CloudSim toolkit⁶⁴. CloudSim toolkit uses generic application provisioning techniques that may be easily and quickly extended. Currently, it offers modelling and simulation of Cloud computing environments that include both single and inter-networked clouds (federation of clouds). It also exposes custom interfaces for implementing policies and provisioning strategies for virtual machine allocation under inter-networked Cloud computing scenarios.

On the one hand, CloudSim offers classes that represent data centers, physical hosts, virtual machines, services to be implemented in data centers, cloud service users and internal data center networks. On the other hand, CloudSim supports dynamic insertion of simulation elements as well as providing message-passing applications and data center network topology⁶⁵. CloudSim also supports the modelling and simulation of various cloud computing environments, as well as the simulation of numerous data centers. Furthermore, research from the literature indicates that CloudSim can instantiate 100,000 machines in less than 5 minutes⁶⁶.

The CloudSim simulator has a multi-layered design⁶⁷. The several layers of CloudSim are depicted in Figure 4.

1. **Network Layer:** This layer of CloudSim is responsible for making communication possible between different layers. This layer also identifies how resources are placed and managed in a cloud environment.
2. **Cloud Resources:** In the cloud environment, this layer includes many primary resources such as data centers and cloud coordinators (which ensure that diverse cloud resources may collaborate).
3. **Cloud Services:** This layer comprises the different services provided to cloud service users. The various cloud services include: Information as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS).
4. **User Interface:** This layer provides the users' interaction with the simulator.

⁶⁴ S. Rizwana and M. Sasikumar, "Cloud Simulation Tools: A Comparative Analysis," in *International Journal of Computer Applications* (0975–8887), International conference on Green Computing and Technology, 2013, pp. 11–14.

⁶⁵ R. Buyya, R. Ranjan, and R. N. Calheiros, "Modeling and simulation of scalable Cloud computing environments and the CloudSim toolkit: Challenges and opportunities," in *2009 international conference on high performance computing & simulation*, 2009, pp. 1–11; R. Buyya, A. Beloglazov, and J. Abawajy, "Energy-efficient management of data center resources for cloud computing: a vision, architectural elements, and open challenges," *ArXiv Prepr. ArXiv10060308*, 2010.

⁶⁶ G. Sakellari and G. Loukas, "A survey of mathematical models, simulation approaches and testbeds used for research in cloud computing," *Simul. Model. Pract. Theory*, vol. 39, pp. 92–103, 2013.

⁶⁷ K. Gupta, R. Beri, V. Behal, K. Gupta, R. Beri, and V. Behal, "Cloud computing: a survey on cloud simulation tools," *Int. J. Innov. Res. Sci. Technol. IJIRST*, vol. 2, no. 11, 2016.

Figure 4 Architecture of CloudSim⁶⁸

- **Eve**

Eve is a web-based multipurpose agent platform that makes use of existing web technologies. They provide a platform for the development of software agents. Eve is an open and dynamic environment in which agents can live and act: in the cloud, on smartphones, on desktops, in browsers, robots, home automation devices, and others. The agents communicate with one another using simple, existing protocols (JSON-RPC) via existing transport layers (HTTP, XMPP), providing a language and platform agnostic solution. Eve is a communication protocol and an agent model that may be implemented in a variety of programming languages and runtime infrastructures.

- **EcoLab**

EcoLab is the name of a software program as well as a research project focused on the evolution of dynamics. EcoLab is an object-oriented simulation environment that performs an experiment-oriented metaphor. It includes a set of instruments that may be used in conjunction with the user's C++ model to visualize the model at runtime, as well as support for distributing agents over an arbitrary topology graph partitioned across several processors, as well as checkpoint and restart support. Furthermore, ClassDesc and GraphCode are two powerful components of the EcoLab programming system. EcoLab was created in order to simulate a specific model — the EcoLab model of an abstract ecology. However, the software has been used to implement a variety of alternative models, indicating its general-purpose nature.

⁶⁸ R. N. Calheiros, R. Ranjan, A. Beloglazov, C. A. De Rose, and R. Buyya, "CloudSim: a toolkit for modeling and simulation of cloud computing environments and evaluation of resource provisioning algorithms," *Softw. Pract. Exp.*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 23–50, 2011.

- **CybelePro**

CybelePro is a commercial agent infrastructure which is used for applications such as modelling and simulation, data mining, robotics, planning and scheduling, data mining, and control of air and ground transportation systems, communication networks and cross-enterprise systems.

Each CybelePro agent is an autonomous entity that resides on a physical machine and can be divided into one or more activities that act as functional units⁶⁹. Two different agents' activities can only communicate by sending messages to each other; such messages can contain arbitrary data. Internal messages (which are more efficient because they are transmitted within the confines of a single Java Virtual Machine) and even sharing references to Java objects are available to activities within the same agent. Each message (whether regular or internal) is sent along some channel; in order to receive its messages, an activity must subscribe to a given channel.

Activities can execute sections of Java code (so-called callbacks) at various points in the simulation in order to conduct useful work; any such execution is referred to as an event, and events are divided into three categories. When an activity receives a message, a message event is triggered. Similarly, an internal event is triggered by an internal message. Finally, timer events aren't triggered by messages; instead, they occur at specified times in the simulation. To execute timer events, an activity must first subscribe to a timer (which is similar to subscribing to a channel) in order to define the future time(s) when the events will take place.

- **AnyLogic**

AnyLogic (AnyLogic: Multimethod Simulation Software, 2016) is a unique tool that combines System Dynamics, Discrete Event, and Agent-Based modelling methods into a one model development environment, allowing the AnyLogic software to provide a great deal of flexibility with its built-in Java capabilities, as all of the simulation's complex agent behaviour can be modelled with Java coding⁷⁰. The three methods can be used in any combination, with one software, to simulate business systems of any complexity. In AnyLogic, various visual modelling languages can be used: process flowcharts, state charts, action charts, and stock & flow diagrams. AnyLogic was the first tool to introduce multimethod simulation modelling and remained the only software with that capability.

Traditional simulation methodologies include system dynamics and discrete event simulation, whereas agent-based simulation is a newer one. In terms of technology, the system dynamics approach focuses on continuous processes, whereas discrete event and agent-based models work mostly in discrete time, i.e. jump from one event to another.

AnyLogic can be used in order to mix multiple simulation methodologies in the same model⁷¹. For example, a package shipping industry model might be created in which carriers are depicted as agents

⁶⁹ W. Peng, W. Krueger, A. Grushin, P. Carlos, V. Manikonda, and M. Santos, "Graph-based methods for the analysis of large-scale multiagent systems," in Proceedings of The 8th International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems-Volume 1, 2009, pp. 545–552.

⁷⁰ "Features." <https://www.anylogic.com/features/> (accessed Jun. 11, 2021).

⁷¹ A. Djanatliev, R. German, P. Kolominsky-Rabas, and B. M. Hofmann, "Hybrid simulation with loosely coupled system dynamics and agent-based models for prospective health technology assessments," in Proceedings of the 2012 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC), 2012, pp. 1–12.

acting/reacting independently, while the inner workings of their transport and infrastructure networks could be modelled with discrete event simulation.

Agents are the main building blocks of this AnyLogic model. An agent is a unit of model design that can have behaviour, memory (history), timing, contacts, etc. The agent's internal state and behaviour can be implemented in several ways⁷². The state of the agent can be represented by a few variables, by the statechart state, etc. The behaviour can be, so to say, passive (e.g., there are agents that only react to message arrivals or to function calls and do not have their own timing), or active, when internal dynamics (timeouts or system dynamics processes) of the agent causes it to act. In the latter case, agents most probably would have an event and/or state chart objects inside.

The METICOS project aims to use a range of different methods and existing simulation tools, providing an entirely new simulation platform that would be linked to the other tools and engines within the same environment to help achieve the final objectives of monitoring parameters values from time to time and support decision making process for the end-users.

In the following subsection, a state-of-the-art of social sensing and its application domain are analyzed.

3.4 Social sensing

3.4.1 An overview of “Sensing”

There are no standard descriptions of sensors or the sensing process. The definitions that are provided are frequently influenced by application perspectives. Generally, a sensor can be described as a device that receives a stimulus and responds with an electrical signal⁷³. Sensor definitions from a scientific or engineering perspective widen the range of possible output signals to include, for example, an optical signal: A device that responds to a physical input with a recordable, functionally related output, usually electrical or optical⁷⁴. Another popular form, which considers the observational element of the measurement, characterizes a sensor as follows: A sensor is a device that converts a physical measure into a signal that can be read by a human or an instrument⁷⁵.

This Deliverable focuses on social sensing, with the goal to identify patterns and indicators of the travellers' and border control staff's behaviour in order to understand if Smart border technologies will be accepted or not.

3.4.2 Types of sensing and use

The first type of “Sensing” is “remote sensing”, which is the process of detecting and monitoring of physical environment by measuring its' reflected and emitted radiation from a distance (typically from

⁷² “1. Creating agent types | AnyLogic Help.” <https://anylogic.help/tutorials/turbine-maintenance/1-different-types-of-agents.html> (accessed Jun. 22, 2021).

⁷³ J. Fraden, Handbook of modern sensors, vol. 3. Springer, 2010.

⁷⁴ D. P. Jones, Biomedical sensors. Momentum press, 2010.

⁷⁵ L. Chen, J. Hoey, C. D. Nugent, D. J. Cook, and Z. Yu, “Sensor-based activity recognition,” IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern. Part C Appl. Rev., vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 790–808, 2012.

satellite or aircraft)⁷⁶. For example, researchers acquire remotely sensed photos from Earth by using special cameras. The second type of sensing is referred to as "social sensing" through online social media sources; social sensing is utilized to examine phenomena in the offline "real" world. In the case of social sensing data, each individual acts as a sensor⁷⁷.

- Remote sensing technology

Remote sensing is a geospatial technology that collects and analyzes electromagnetic (EM) radiation emitted and reflected by the Earth's terrestrial, atmospheric, and aquatic ecosystems in order to detect and monitor the physical properties of a location without making physical contact⁷⁸. This data collection method typically employs aircraft- and satellite-based sensor technologies, which are classified as either passive or active sensors.

Passive sensors respond to external stimuli by collecting radiation reflected or emitted by an object or the surrounding environment. One of the most common sources of radiation is reflected sunlight measured by passive remote sensing. Charge-coupled devices, film photography, radiometers, and infrared are all examples of passive remote sensors.

Active sensors collect data by emitting energy to scan objects and areas, after which a sensor measures the energy reflected from the target. Active remote sensing tools such as RADAR and LiDAR use the time delay between emission and return to determine an object's location, direction, and speed. Then, by using remote sensing hardware and computer software, the collected remote sensing data is processed and analyzed, which are available in a variety of open-source applications.

- Social sensing

All citizens become part of an extensive sensor network that is low-cost, more comprehensive, and constantly broadcasts situational awareness thanks to social sensing. Social sensing data, on the other hand, are often huge, heterogeneous, noisy, and inaccurate in some ways. It comes in continuous streams and often lacks geospatial reference data. Together, these issues represent a grand challenge toward fully leveraging social sensing for emergency management decision making under extreme duress. Furthermore, human involvement in the sensing process may result in subjective sensing outcomes, trust issues, errors, and privacy concerns.

Technologies and big data computing methods such as multi-source data fusion, deep learning and high-performance computing constitute basic components of using social sensing to provide a step-change toward more modern and efficient Smart Border management, as well as gaining societal and political acceptance of modern EU border control technologies such as "no gate solutions."

⁷⁶ Y. Liu et al., "Social sensing: A new approach to understanding our socioeconomic environments," *Ann. Assoc. Am. Geogr.*, vol. 105, no. 3, pp. 512–530, 2015.

⁷⁷ J. An and I. Weber, "Whom should we sense in 'social sensing'-analyzing which users work best for social media now-casting," *EPJ Data Sci.*, vol. 4, pp. 1–22, 2015.

⁷⁸ Y. Liu et al., "Social sensing: A new approach to understanding our socioeconomic environments," *Ann. Assoc. Am. Geogr.*, vol. 105, no. 3, pp. 512–530, 2015.

3.4.3 Social sensing

In general, social sensing refers to a set of sensing and data collection examples in which data are collected from humans or devices. In order to provide situation-awareness to applications, social sensing services use humans as sensor carriers, sensor operators, and sensors themselves. Due to the advance in the Internet of Things (IoT), smart gadgets, and ubiquitous computing, social sensing enables the collection of multi-modal interaction data on an unprecedented scale. In a variety of applications⁷⁹ social sensing technologies have been used. Their insights help in the study of human behaviour, as well as enable an analysis of social interaction structures and structural modelling.

Social sensing predates the use of physical, technological sensors and social media in terms of technology⁸⁰. For centuries, words have been used in order to communicate observed experiences to others, whether in oral or written form, for various reasons. Messages in these types of communications may be explicit or implicit. Scholars, for example, may have discovered hidden messages inside Plato's works⁸¹. What is different today is that technology has made it much easier to formulate and express thoughts that are immediately accessible to the entire world.

The emergence of big data has opened up new opportunities for understanding our socioeconomic environments⁸². Online social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn have democratized information dissemination, allowing anyone to share information about themselves and their surroundings on an unprecedented scale. The large volume of information thus posted on these media provides a new lens into the physical world through social media platforms. The use of this lens to examine aspects of the global state has recently been termed "social sensing"⁸³. The massive amount of data shared on platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, etc., provides a new perspective on the real world from the lenses of the social network. With increased dissemination power comes a greater risk of misuse. It is now not only much easier to share ideas, but it is also becoming increasingly possible to exploit people's views of reality on a massive scale. Finding and understanding the valuable and honest messages in the much larger amount of social media material is thus becoming an increasing challenge today.

⁷⁹ Y. Liu et al., "Social sensing: A new approach to understanding our socioeconomic environments," *Ann. Assoc. Am. Geogr.*, vol. 105, no. 3, pp. 512–530, 2015.; C. C. Aggarwal and T. Abdelzaher, "Social sensing," in *Managing and mining sensor data*, Springer, 2013, pp. 237–297.; M. Atzmueller, M. Becker, and J. Mueller, "Collective sensing platforms," in *Participatory Sensing, Opinions and Collective Awareness*, Springer, 2017, pp. 115–133.; M. Atzmueller and K. Hilgenberg, "Towards capturing social interactions with sdcf: An extensible framework for mobile sensing and ubiquitous data collection," in *Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Modeling Social Media*, 2013, pp. 1–4.; N. Eagle and A. S. Pentland, "Reality mining: sensing complex social systems," *Pers. Ubiquitous Comput.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 255–268, 2006.; L. Isella et al., "Close encounters in a pediatric ward: measuring face-to-face proximity and mixing patterns with wearable sensors," *PLoS One*, vol. 6, no. 2, p. e17144, 2011.; A. Madan, M. Cebrian, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, "Social sensing for epidemiological behavior change," in *Proceedings of the 12th ACM international conference on Ubiquitous computing*, 2010, pp. 291–300.; A. Madan, S. T. Moturu, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, "Social sensing: obesity, unhealthy eating and exercise in face-to-face networks," in *Wireless Health 2010*, 2010, pp. 104–110.; M. Salathe et al., "Digital epidemiology," *PLoS Comput Biol*, vol. 8, no. 7, p. e1002616, 2012.

⁸⁰ D. Wang, T. Abdelzaher, and L. Kaplan, *Social sensing: building reliable systems on unreliable data*. Morgan Kaufmann, 2015.

⁸¹ J. B. Kennedy, "Plato's Forms, Pythagorean Mathematics, and Stochometry," *Apeiron*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 1–32, 2010.

⁸² Y. Liu et al., "Social sensing: A new approach to understanding our socioeconomic environments," *Ann. Assoc. Am. Geogr.*, vol. 105, no. 3, pp. 512–530, 2015.

⁸³ D. Wang, B. K. Szymanski, T. Abdelzaher, H. Ji, and L. Kaplan, "The age of social sensing," *Computer*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 36–45, 2019.

3.4.4 Social sensing media sources

With more organizations and individuals having access to the Internet, the use of social media and social networking websites has increased rapidly in recent years⁸⁴. There are more social media platforms available, and more people, corporations, and other organizations are using them⁸⁵. As a result, online interaction is a regular part of daily life for a demographically diverse population of billions of people around the world⁸⁶. Users of social media can share their ideas, feelings, and/or opinions on nearly any topic⁸⁷. Also, by having access to measurements from multiple locations or communities, models trained on text data from social media can be used both in order to predict future measurements and to provide community estimates where these are lacking or are not robust⁸⁸.

For the METICOS project, corporate websites and social media sources such as Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn, as well as other open-source information, will be used for identifying patterns of information in travellers' behaviour in order to predict acceptance of BCP technologies.

- **Facebook:** Facebook has indeed various tools that provide a medium for social sensing. Opinion Polls, for example, are platforms that allow users to survey their friends' opinions. Facebook also has Hashtag Pages, similar to Twitter, where Facebook posts labelled with a specific keyword are collected in a single Facebook page, and the available data can be used for social sensing. However, more importantly, the most authentic Facebook social sensing mechanism is based on user interactions via user walls, which are Facebook pages where users can add comments or like posts shared by their friends. The discussion of the opinions through these interactions on Facebook results in a comment thread, which is a collection of user posts⁸⁹. The comment thread is a medium for social sensing since it facilitates the collection of the opinions of Facebook users on a specific event, which may be estimated using the posts in the comment thread.
- **Twitter:** Twitter is one of the most dynamic SNS (Social networking sites) with respect to the interactions among users and one of the most powerful with respect to the potential information that can be extracted for sharing experiences, discussing opinions etc. Compared to other SNS (Facebook, Instagram, etc.), it has a simple data model and a straightforward data access API. Furthermore, Twitter data, in comparison with other social media platforms such as Facebook, are more openly accessible and, for a proportion of tweets, can contain valuable metadata.
- **LinkedIn:** LinkedIn is a business-oriented social networking site that was created in 2003 with the goal of allowing registered users to maintain a list of contact details of people they know and trust in business, referred to as connections. The user's social network is determined by their list of connections. Each registered user gives free text for both personal and professional

⁸⁴ "Information and communication technology (ICT) - Internet access - OECD Data," theOECD. <http://data.oecd.org/ict/internet-access.htm> (accessed Aug. 02, 2021).

⁸⁵ B. Nyagadza, "Search engine marketing and social media marketing predictive trends," J. Digit. Media Policy, 2020.

⁸⁶ S. A. Golder and M. W. Macy, "Digital footprints: Opportunities and challenges for online social research," *Annu. Rev. Sociol.*, vol. 40, pp. 129–152, 2014.

⁸⁷ C. Chew and G. Eysenbach, "Pandemics in the age of Twitter: content analysis of Tweets during the 2009 H1N1 outbreak," *PloS One*, vol. 5, no. 11, p. e14118, 2010.

⁸⁸ A. Kumar, A. Sharma, and A. Arora, "Anxious depression prediction in real-time social data," 2019.

⁸⁹ L. Backstrom, J. Kleinberg, L. Lee, and C. Danescu-Niculescu-Mizil, "Characterizing and curating conversation threads: expansion, focus, volume, re-entry," in *Proceedings of the sixth ACM international conference on Web search and data mining*, 2013, pp. 13–22.

information. Specialities (professional skills), Interests, and Groups and Associations affiliated with the user, are frequently exploited among professional data, which have been proved very important sources for improving collaborative filtering systems⁹⁰.

3.4.5 The domain of Social Sensing

Social Sensing is being applied to many areas, such as Healthcare, Smart buildings, Mobile Sensing, Behavior Analysis etc. Some application domains of social sensing and their model description are listed in Table 4, with an exemplar publication for each domain. Some studies in which social sensing is used, are analyzed below.

Social Sensing has been widely used in the domain of Healthcare. In a study⁹¹, authors implemented social sensing in order to investigate the impact that social interactions in real-world face-to-face networks have on BMI and weight changes in a co-located student community. *It was found that exposure measured using Bluetooth proximity to peers that are overweight or obese and to peers that have unhealthy dietary habits or inactive lifestyles, can influence weight changes in an individual as opposed to exposure to close friends and social acquaintances.*

In⁹², the authors proposed a framework for highly distributed and user-centric air quality monitoring, designed to involve the citizen in multiple stages of the monitoring process. The goal of the study was to enable individuals to monitor their exposure to air pollution, at the same time contributing to the construction of a map of the state of urban air quality through the sharing of data. *This study showed that mobile sensing could play an important role for public health, as citizens by monitoring their exposure to air pollution, can improve air quality.*

Rashid et al.⁹³ present SocialDrone, a novel closed-loop social-physical active sensing framework that integrates social sensing with drone-based physical sensing for reliable disaster response. Specifically, in SocialDrone, signals emitted from social media are distilled to drive the drones to target areas to verify the emergency events. The verification results are then taken back to improve the sensing and distillation process on social media. The results from this study showed that the SocialDrone scheme significantly outperforms both the social only and drone only systems. *Furthermore, this study shows the important role of social media sensing as it emits signals to SocialDrone for checking emergency events.*

In another study, Kibanov et al.⁹⁴ investigate the opportunities that social media sensing offers for improved management of peatland fire and haze disasters. Specifically, Twitter was analyzed as the primary data source for haze disaster management by extracting complementary and supplementary information and hotspot and air quality data were used in order to interpret further and verify the

⁹⁰ D. H. Lee and P. Brusilovsky, "Using self-defined group activities for improving recommendations in collaborative tagging systems," in Proceedings of the fourth ACM conference on Recommender systems, 2010, pp. 221–224.

⁹¹ A. Madan, S. T. Moturu, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, "Social sensing: obesity, unhealthy eating and exercise in face-to-face networks," in Wireless Health 2010, 2010, pp. 104–110.

⁹² A. Madan, S. T. Moturu, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, "Social sensing: obesity, unhealthy eating and exercise in face-to-face networks," in Wireless Health 2010, 2010, pp. 104–110.

⁹³ M. T. Rashid, D. Y. Zhang, and D. Wang, "Socialdrone: An integrated social media and drone sensing system for reliable disaster response," in [IEEE INFOCOM 2020-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, 2020, pp. 218–227.](#)

⁹⁴ M. Kibanov, G. Stumme, I. Amin, and J. G. Lee, "Mining social media to inform peatland fire and haze disaster management," Soc. Netw. Anal. Min., vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–19, 2017.

results of the study. *In this study, the role of Twitter is important as social sensing source as it shows: 1) how users of Twitter react to haze emergencies and found correlations between the public discourse on Twitter and peat fire hotspots, 2) how it is possible to understand the changes in users' travel patterns during haze periods using social media and 3) how social media data can be used in order to inform disaster management at different stages of an emergency.*

Avvenuti et al.⁹⁵ mentioned the possibility of predicting natural disasters using social media data. Specifically, they discussed a system that is based on Twitter data for the detection and damage assessment of earthquakes in Italy. *This study showed a strong correlation between earthquake intensity and tweet-derived predictors that means Twitter as social sensing sources play a significant role in predicting natural disasters.*

In another study, Madan et al.⁹⁶, use mobile phone-based co-location and communication sensing to measure characteristic behaviour changes in symptomatic individuals, reflected in their total communication, interactions with respect to time of day (e.g., late-night, early morning), diversity and entropy of face-to-face interactions and movement, in order to understand how individual behaviour is affected by illness and stress. Specifically, mobile phones were used as an active sensing and prediction platform to identify behaviour changes reflected in mobile phone sensors, when individuals suffer from illnesses. The results showed that it is possible to determine the health status of individuals using information gathered by mobile phones alone, without having actual health measurements about the subject. *This study showed that mobile sensing could play an important role in modelling epidemiological contagion without medical health reports.*

D'Andrea et al.⁹⁷ present a real-time monitoring system for traffic event detection from Twitter stream analysis. The system fetches tweets from Twitter according to several search criteria; processes tweets, by applying text mining techniques; and finally performs the classification of tweets. The aim of the study was to assign the appropriate class label to each tweet, as related to a traffic event or not. The traffic detection system was employed for real-time monitoring of several areas of the Italian road network. The results showed that the system which was built in the study, was able to fetch and classify streams of tweets and to notify the users of the presence of traffic events. Furthermore, the system was able to discriminate if a traffic event is due to an external cause (such as football match, procession and manifestation, or not). *This study showed that in the domain of traffic monitoring, social media sources such as Twitter could be used for traffic event detection in real-time before online traffic news websites.*

Additional social sensing publications in each of the application domains are available- listed in Table 4, along with many domain areas where social sensing modelling has been successfully applied.

Table 4 Application Domain of Social Sensing

⁹⁵ M. Avvenuti, S. Cresci, A. Marchetti, C. Meletti, and M. Tesconi, "Predictability or early warning: using social media in modern emergency response," *IEEE Internet Comput.*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 4–6, 2016.

⁹⁶ A. Madan, M. Cebrian, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, "Social sensing for epidemiological behavior change," in *Proceedings of the 12th ACM international conference on Ubiquitous computing*, 2010, pp. 291–300.

⁹⁷ E. D'Andrea, P. Ducange, B. Lazzerini, and F. Marcelloni, "Real-time detection of traffic from twitter stream analysis," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 2269–2283, 2015.

Application Domain	Model Description	Authors	Year
<i>Mobile Sensing</i>	Social sensing for Mobile systems using data taken from social media for online news ⁹⁸	Rashid, M. T., & Wang, D.	2020
<i>Events Analysis</i>	Social sensing and big data computing for disaster management ⁹⁹	Li, Z., Huang, Q., & Emrich, C. T. (Eds.).	2017
<i>Disaster Management</i>	Mining social media to inform peatland fire and haze disaster management ¹⁰⁰	Kibanov, M., Stumme, G., Amin, I., & Lee, J. G.	2017
<i>Traffic and Urban Activity Monitoring</i>	A social sensing model for traffic detection system of the Italian road network ¹⁰¹	Ducange, P., & Fazzolari, M.	2017
<i>Emergency Event</i>	Predictability or early warning: using social media in modern emergency response ¹⁰²	Avvenuti, M., Cresci, S., Marchetti, A., Meletti, C., & Tesconi, M.	2016
<i>Smart Buildings</i>	Social sensing approach to the distributed monitoring of air quality ¹⁰³	Capezzuto, L., Abbamonte, L., De Vito, S., Massera.	2015
<i>Traffic Monitoring</i>	Real-time detection of traffic from twitter stream analysis ¹⁰⁴	D'Andrea, E., Ducange, P., Lazzerini, B., & Marcelloni, F.	2015

⁹⁸M. T. Rashid, D. Y. Zhang, and D. Wang, "Socialdrone: An integrated social media and drone sensing system for reliable disaster response," in IEEE INFOCOM 2020-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, 2020, pp. 218–227.

⁹⁹Z. Li, Q. Huang, and C. T. Emrich, Introduction to social sensing and big data computing for disaster management. Taylor & Francis, 2019.

¹⁰⁰M. Kibanov, G. Stumme, I. Amin, and J. G. Lee, "Mining social media to inform peatland fire and haze disaster management," Soc. Netw. Anal. Min., vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–19, 2017.

¹⁰¹P. Ducange and M. Fazzolari, "Social sensing and sentiment analysis: Using social media as useful information source," in 2017 International Conference on Smart Systems and Technologies (SST), 2017, pp. 301–306.

¹⁰²M. Avvenuti, S. Cresci, A. Marchetti, C. Meletti, and M. Tesconi, "Predictability or early warning: using social media in modern emergency response," IEEE Internet Comput., vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 4–6, 2016.

¹⁰³I. Capezzuto et al., "An app based air quality social sensing system built on open source Hw/Sw tools," in Sensors, Springer, 2015, pp. 309–313.

¹⁰⁴E. D'Andrea, P. Ducange, B. Lazzerini, and F. Marcelloni, "Real-time detection of traffic from twitter stream analysis," IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst., vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 2269–2283, 2015.

<i>Behaviour Analysis</i>	Social Sensing for Epidemiological Behavior Change ¹⁰⁵	Madan, A., Cebrian, M., Lazer, D., & Pentland, A.	2010
<i>Healthcare</i>	Social Sensing for Obesity, Unhealthy Eating and Exercise in Face-to-Face Networks ¹⁰⁶	Madan, A., Moturu, S. T., Lazer, D., & Pentland, A	2010

Although there isn't such research work available in the domain of ABC technologies, previous applications and methodologies of social sensing at different domains, will help border control technologies, as *technology acceptance will be monitored considering the different demographics and profile data of the travellers and their perceptions during their interactions with the border control technologies while passing the EU border control systems.*"

3.4.6 Technology Enablers of social sensing

In order to fulfil the main objectives of the METICOS project, social sensing will be based upon the following: 1) Data collection through the web, online social networks, real-time data from borders, 2) Understanding the important data attributes and contribution to the toolkit and 3) Finding patterns from the data. This type of technology could be developed near border crossing points, for example, by extracting data from social media such as Facebook, Twitter, Reddit etc. and questionnaires which will be filled out by passengers.

Sensors and social networks can now be combined thanks to recent technological developments in hardware and software. The creation of small mobile sensors that can capture a range of user-specific information such as audio or video is one such key technological advancement. Many of the applications listed are based on the position of the user. With the use of mobile GPS-enabled devices, such a location can be easily computed. Most recent smartphones, for example, have GPS technology embedded inside them¹⁰⁷. Situation-aware applications use data streams from sensors in order to offer useful services to users or other applications. The potential of such applications is expanding with the proliferation of sensors deployed in the surrounding world, such as through the Internet of Things. Recently, the focus of research has been expanded from traditional fixed sensor deployments toward social sensing¹⁰⁸. This includes passive sensors in Smart Phones provided by human carriers, active human sensor operators taking pictures or videos, and even humans operating as sensors, such as

¹⁰⁵ A. Madan, M. Cebrian, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, "Social sensing for epidemiological behavior change," in Proceedings of the 12th ACM international conference on Ubiquitous computing, 2010, pp. 291–300.

¹⁰⁶ A. Madan, S. T. Moturu, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, "Social sensing: obesity, unhealthy eating and exercise in face-to-face networks," in Wireless Health 2010, 2010, pp. 104–110.

¹⁰⁷ J. Lifton, M. Feldmeier, Y. Ono, C. Lewis, and J. A. Paradiso, "A platform for ubiquitous sensor deployment in occupational and domestic environments," in [Proceedings of the 6th international conference on Information processing in sensor networks, 2007, pp. 119–127.](#); M. Laibowitz, N.-W. Gong, and J. A. Paradiso, "Wearable sensing for dynamic management of dense ubiquitous media," in 2009 Sixth International Workshop on Wearable and Implantable Body Sensor Networks, 2009, pp. 3–8.

¹⁰⁸ H. Kopka and W. Patrick, [DALY, A Guide to LaTeX. Addison-Wesley, 1999.](#)

providing live information in tweets and postings. New applications that use the social sensing infrastructure to infer situations that are not detectable by traditional sensors have recently been proposed¹⁰⁹.

Sensors usually collect large amounts of data, which must be stored and analysed on a continuous basis. Furthermore, since the number of users in a social network can be very high, scalability issues for the storage and processing of the underlying streams arise naturally. Because of the large number of streams that are continuously obtained, many naive solutions, such as centralized storage and processing of raw streams, are not very realistic. A number of recent hardware and software advances have proven to be very useful in dealing with this issue, such as:

- Development of Miniaturized Sensor Technology
- Advancement of smartphone technology
- Increased Bandwidth
- Increased Storage
- Development of Fast Stream Processing Platforms
- Development of Stream Synopsis Algorithms and Software

3.5 Technology acceptance

Users' attitudes influence the adoption and the acceptance of emerging technologies, which is referred to as Technology Acceptance. The technology acceptance model (TAM) is an information theory that models the adoption and usage of technology by individual persons. Since emerging technologies, such as personal computers (such as personal computers) are complex, and decision-makers are unsure about their successful adoption of them, people develop attitudes and intentions toward attempting to learn to use the new technology before beginning efforts directed at using. Attitudes and intentions toward the use of technology may be ill-formed or unconvinced, or they may occur only after a series of preliminary attempts to learn how to use the technology¹¹⁰. As a result, practical use may not be a direct or immediate result of these behaviours and intentions¹¹¹. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was designed to test technology acceptance¹¹². According to TAM (Figure 5), the success of the new technology adoption is based on positive attitudes towards two measures: 1) perceived utility and 2) perceived ease of use. Its origins can be traced back to Ajzen and Fishbein (2), who developed 'Theory of Reasoned Action,' but Davis wanted a more user-friendly model to look at technology at

¹⁰⁹ R. Mayer, H. Gupta, E. Saurez, and U. Ramachandran, "The fog makes sense: Enabling social sensing services with limited internet connectivity," in Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Social Sensing, 2017, pp. 61–66.

¹¹⁰ R. P. Bagozzi, F. D. Davis, and P. R. Warshaw, "Development and test of a theory of technological learning and usage," *Hum. Relat.*, vol. 45, no. 7, pp. 659–686, 1992.

¹¹¹ R. P. Bagozzi, F. D. Davis, and P. R. Warshaw, "Development and test of a theory of technological learning and usage," *Hum. Relat.*, vol. 45, no. 7, pp. 659–686, 1992.

¹¹² F. D. Davis, R. P. Bagozzi, and P. R. Warshaw, "User acceptance of computer technology: A comparison of two theoretical models," *Manag. Sci.*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 982–1003, 1989.

work. Many researchers have since created and expanded this model, making more complex models, but the original model is still used and widely accepted as a leading model in understanding users' actions towards technology.

Figure 5 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989) [94]

Furthermore, because of the development of various competing acceptance models, in 2003, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) was developed¹¹³. Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, Social Influence and Facilitating Conditions are the four components identified as determining factors for behavioural intention. The influence of the four aforementioned factors is moderated by gender, age, experience and voluntariness of use.

3.5.1 Technology acceptance for border control technologies

Data-driven monitoring and prediction acceptance of different BCP technologies helps to identify likely roll-out and adoption problems early. It also enables the identification of similar behavioural clusters of users and the tracking of trends in real-time, and the analysis of how different target groups and entities may relate and respond to the intentions, feelings and actions/decisions of others in the short and long run¹¹⁴.

Although the BCP technologies systems have been in use since the beginning of this century, there is no standardization of the main components, with user interfaces still being under development. From a survey¹¹⁵, the main issues related to passport scanners was due to the problem of the incomprehensible user interface. BCP systems are not user-friendly because instructions aren't understood by first-time user¹¹⁶. So, as a result, many of the passengers would get confused and irritated, causing delays and frustration in the queue behind them, because they don't know the "exact" place for scanning their passport.

¹¹³ V. Venkatesh, M. G. Morris, G. B. Davis, and F. D. Davis, "User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view," *MIS Q.*, pp. 425–478, 2003.

¹¹⁴ A.-M. Oostveen, M. Kaufmann, E. Krempel, and G. Grasemann, "Automated border control: a comparative usability study at two European airports," 2014.

¹¹⁵ M. Ylikaupila, S. Toivonen, M. Kulju, and M. Jokela, "Understanding the factors affecting UX and technology acceptance in the context of automated border controls," in 2014 IEEE Joint Intelligence and Security Informatics Conference, 2014, pp. 168–175.

¹¹⁶ A.-M. Oostveen, M. Kaufmann, E. Krempel, and G. Grasemann, "Automated border control: a comparative usability study at two European airports," 2014.

In addition, information and clear signs about how BCP technologies are used by passengers play an important role in increasing general awareness of BCP systems, encouraging passengers to use the system and guide them successfully through the process. Gate’s design from the user’s view is the main factor affecting how easily the function of the system is recognised, and usage learned. Travel documents and biometrics are the instruments for interaction between passengers and technology.

User acceptance demands that the users perceive a real need for the e-gates (e.g. convenience) and that the system is easy to use. This is particularly true when the users need to interact with new technologies infrequently or in unusual complex situations, such as travelling in an unknown context, under stress and fatigue¹¹⁷. Users are currently confused about how to interact with unfamiliar and various e-gates due to significant component differences. Standardization will be vital for improving traveller usability and raising user confidence. Positive experiences of users are vital as they lead to repetition and can have a favourable impact on the uptake of the technology by current non-users through word-of-mouth endorsement.

Acceptance modelling based on TAM or UTAUT in the context of border control technologies focuses on specific aspects of border control systems, such as biometrics. The authors of¹¹⁸ explore the factors that influence the behavioural intention to accept biometrics. The proposed model (Figure 6), according to the authors of the paper, identifies the links between factors such as innovativeness, trust, and privacy concerns), antecedent factors (such as beliefs about the technology and other variables such as social influence and facilitating conditions, as well as the two subsequent factors of intentions to accept and to recommend using the biometric system¹¹⁹. For a detailed overview, please see a.

Figure 6 Acceptance model for biometric technology¹²⁰

¹¹⁷ G. Pirelli, “Usability in public services and border control,” in Symposium of the Austrian HCI and Usability Engineering Group, 2009, pp. 532–552.

¹¹⁸ C. L. Miltgen, A. Popovič, and T. Oliveira, “Determinants of end-user acceptance of biometrics: Integrating the ‘Big 3’ of technology acceptance with privacy context,” *Decis. Support Syst.*, vol. 56, pp. 103–114, 2013.

¹¹⁹ For a detailed review please see: M. Scott, T. Acton, and M. Hughes, “An assessment of biometric identities as a standard for e-government services,” *Int. J. Serv. Stand.*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 271–286, 2005.; S. A. Shaikh and J. R. Rabaiotti, “Characteristic trade-offs in designing large-scale biometric-based identity management systems,” *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 342–351, 2010.; A. Taneja, A. Wang, and M. K. Raja, “Assessing the impact of concern for privacy and innovation characteristics in the adoption of biometric technologies,” 2006.

¹²⁰ C. L. Miltgen, A. Popovič, and T. Oliveira, “Determinants of end-user acceptance of biometrics: Integrating the ‘Big 3’ of technology acceptance with privacy context,” *Decis. Support Syst.*, vol. 56, pp. 103–114, 2013.

4 Functional and operational requirements

This section discusses the functional and operational requirements (based on a State of the Art review) that are relevant for the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit. In particular, this section includes: 1) data categories template, 2) overall methods of data collection, 3) requirements for social sensing source, 4) requirements of the agent-based simulation tool and 5) identification of social sensing techniques that will be used for the social sensing toolkit.

4.1 Social Sensing Toolkit

METICOS WP6 focuses on social sensing toolkit, with the purpose of accessing and assessing travellers' and border control staffs' perceptions, emotional states, and social interactions in order to determine whether or not the border technology will be adopted and accepted, and if so, how effectively. WP6's major purpose is to predict technology acceptance; nevertheless, it is not about determining whether or not a technology in use is being accepted, or how well it is being accepted. Border-control authorities will monitor and predict acceptance (by travellers and border staff), secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency through METICOS Social Sensing Platform (Figure 7). The overall METICOS Social Sensing composes of three modules, namely Socio-Cultural Framework Module, Data Processing Module and Agent based Simulations Module. The overall architecture receives data that is collected both online and through physical means. The online data sources are Online Social Networks (OSNs) and the physical data sources are in the form of data to be collected at the pilot sites from the pilots, data to be collected from borders (possibly real-time and in the form of traveller/BCP satisfaction, travel documents, etc.), data as SBC technology requirements (such as UI design, process flow, usability, security, trust, etc.) and data coming from BCP\Traveler Questionnaires carried out by WP5.

Socio-Cultural Framework Module (SCFM): This is the module which interfaces the online and physical data sources and identifies patterns (rules) in the data and extract profiles and demographics of persons using borders (travelers) and persons working at the borders (border staff). The rules may be both hands crafted from the data available and can be automatically extracted from data using machine and deep learning techniques. We estimate rules to be in the form of “person profile → a type of perception”. An example synthetic rule would be “a person over age of 80 perceives the biometrics-based verification technology difficult to use”. The rules and the profiles extracted from the data sources are provided as input to the Data Processing Module.

Data Processing Module (DPM): This is the module which mainly extracts perceptions of the travelers and border staff using state-of-the-art techniques. The same data sources are used as inputs to this module as well as the profiles and rules received from the SCFM. Once the perceptions are extracted, these perceptions are paired with profiles coming from the SCFM. That is, we generate a pool of (profile, perception) pairs which will be used for training and validating the Agent based Simulations Module along with the rules already obtained in the SCFM.

The Agent based Simulations Module (ABSM): the idea behind making simulations is twofold: 1) providing a system where actually we can demonstrate that certain profiles are framed by certain perceptions grounded in the data analysis performed in SCFM and SSTM modules. 2) Once we have

the system that can mimic the perceptions of various types of profiles in a realistic way, it can be used to mimic the perceptions of profiles that has not been met before given a set of technologies. That is we can predict border crossing technology acceptance of various users\profiles.

This way we can identify whether age, education level, other types of demographics, crowdedness of the BCP, delays with flights, etc. cause variations in technology acceptance decisions, and furthermore how and why.

As per today, we do not have any data received from most of the sources listed as data sources in Figure , to carry the work. For that reason, we have both collected data from Twitter and also created synthetic data sets to represent rules, and perception and profile pairs for our work to begin. Initial trainings of the Agent based simulations are carried by using these data. In these simulations, we have defined three types of agents: travelers who are passing border crossings, border staff, and the border control technologies. The further details of the experiments (the methodologies for rule, profile and demographics extraction) carried out in the ABSM is explained in the earlier sections of this report already. We have also identified synthetic scenarios for exploring which profiles lead to what kind of technology acceptance decisions. Next step will be to align with the actual scenarios of the METICOS project whose details will be given in D6.3. Along with data to be received from the other unexplored data sources, we will increase the accuracy of technology prediction decisions of the agent-based simulations module.

Figure 7 General architecture of METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit (WP6)¹²¹

4.2 Identification of required data categories and data types

In the context of border control technologies, it is of primary importance to optimize and monitor the flow of people at land, sea and air borders in order to understand their needs and concerns about this new era of smart border control technologies. In the “A comparison of primary stakeholders’ views on the deployment of biometric technologies in border management: Case study of SMart mobility at the

¹²¹ The synthetic data stage is the stage 1 because it works on the random synthetic data. The social sensing stage is the stage 2 as it involves additional real data sources including the online social networks.

*European land borders”*¹²², the authors compare primary stakeholders’ views on the deployment of biometric technologies in land border management. Specifically, their method consisted of in-person interviews with border guards, observation and field visits (to the Hungarian-Romanian and Bulgarian-Romanian borders) and questionnaires for both travellers and border guards. The results showed that border guards argued that biometric technologies had the potential to be a powerful tool for enhancing security levels and making traveller identification and authentication procedures simpler, quicker and more convenient. In addition, travellers find many advantages from using biometric technologies, such as: 1) speeding up the border control processes and reducing their waiting time at the border and 2) facilitating easy and fast border crossing without the need to wait long in queues. On the other hand, travellers were more concerned about technology that threatened fundamental rights, personal privacy, and data security. *This study shows that data collection (field observation, interview, questionnaires) obtained from land border guards and travellers plays an important role in order to investigate and understand participants’ expectations on the use of biometric technologies used in the border’s management.* The authors¹²³ tested the potential of social media to assist disaster management. Specifically, they analyzed Twitter as the primary data source and use hotspot and air quality data to interpret further and verify the results of their analysis. *In this study, the role of Twitter is important as social sensing source as it shows: 1) how users of Twitter react to haze emergencies and found correlations between the public discourse on Twitter and peat fire hotspots, 2) how it is possible to understand the changes in users’ travel patterns during haze periods using social media and 3) how social media data can be used as a valuable source of complementary and supplementary information for haze disaster management.*

In another study¹²⁴, the authors used mobile sensing in order to understand how individual behaviour is affected by illness and stress. The results from this study showed that without obtaining actual health measurements regarding subjects, it is feasible to determine the health status of individuals using only information obtained by mobile phones. *This study showed that mobile sensing could be useful for modelling epidemiological contagion in the absence of medical health reporting.* The authors¹²⁵ studied how a system based on Twitter data can help in detection and damage assessment of earthquake in Italy. Specifically, they mentioned that there is a strong correlation between tweet-derived predictors and earthquake intensity. *This study showed that by using social media (Twitter) data, there is the possibility to predict natural disasters.*

Although there aren’t many studies available in the domain of border management, previous applications and methodologies at different domains help us to define data categories which will be used for social sensing for border control management, in order to monitor views of travellers and border guards using SBCTs.

In this section, we identify the data categories and data types that are required for the development of METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit (Figure 7). Specifically, the METICOS platform will correlate these

¹²² Abomhara, M., Yayilgan, S. Y., Nweke, L. O., & Székely, Z. (2021). A comparison of primary stakeholders’ views on the deployment of biometric technologies in border management: Case study of SMart mobilLity at the European land borders. *Technology in Society*, 64, 101484.

¹²³ M. Kibanov, G. Stumme, I. Amin, and J. G. Lee, “Mining social media to inform peatland fire and haze disaster management,” *Soc. Netw. Anal. Min.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–19, 2017.

¹²⁴ A. Madan, M. Cebrian, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, “Social sensing for epidemiological behavior change,” in *Proceedings of the 12th ACM international conference on Ubiquitous computing*, 2010, pp. 291–300.

¹²⁵ M. Avvenuti, S. Cresci, A. Marchetti, C. Meletti, and M. Tesconi, “Predictability or early warning: using social media in modern emergency response,” *IEEE Internet Comput.*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 4–6, 2016.

types of data from different sources (e.g. social media, websites etc.) in order to validate the technology acceptance, social acceptance and to increase travellers' trust to Smart Border solutions.

4.2.1 Data categories template

Given that the goal of the METICOS platform is to assess users' acceptance of border control technologies as well as measure the efficiency of such technologies, data concerning two different sets of "users" are being collected: a) Data related to travellers and b) Data related to border control staff. The METICOS platform receives data originating from two categories of data sources (Figure 8):

1. **Primary Data:** Primary data is the type of data that is collected directly from informed and consented “users” during the METICOS project activities and during pilots at the Border Control Points. Such primary data originates from:
 - Questionnaires addressing specific questions about border crossing points, their control routines and technologies used;
 - Twitter: After crossing the border in the METICOS pilot site, the user is posting a tweet using a specific hashtag (e.g. #METICOS-EU pilot);
 - METICOS Mobile Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a mobile application;
 - METICOS Tablet Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a tablet application.

2. **Secondary data:** Secondary data is the type of data that is relevant to METICOS but has been collected in the past. Such data are already available to use in the context of the project from existing sources. Such secondary data originates from:
 - Statistical data originating from border crossing points’ databases;
 - Twitter: The aim is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, perceptions and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies.
 - Online reviews of BCPs on blogs/websites (a multi-lingual process will be followed – currently (the time of the current document report, it is taking place in english language).

Additional details on the data that will be collected can be found on D3.1. For WP6, the categories of datasets that are required for the Social Sensing Toolkit are shown in Figure 8 and explained further:

Figure 8 Categories of data required for Social Sensing Toolkit

Anonymization processes applied to primary and secondary data

Article 89 of the GDPR recommends “anonymization” of personal data for scientific research purposes. In the context of the METICOS platform, it is considered that the purpose of the project could be achieved :

- by anonymizing the primary data collected via the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications and questionnaires before presenting the KPIs and metrics to border control authorities and decision-makers;
- by anonymizing the primary and secondary data collected via Twitter before presenting the KPIs and metrics to border control authorities and decision-makers;
- by collecting already anonymized secondary statistical data originating from end-user organizations (Border Control Points).

The choice for the anonymization techniques applied to the previous data categories that will be made are described below:

- *For Primary data collected via the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications and questionnaires*

When collecting primary data via the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications and questionnaires, the joint controllers will not ask for any direct identifiers such as first name, last name, date of birth, etc. In addition, the responsible partners for developing the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications (MAGG) and questionnaires (AIT) will select appropriate anonymization techniques. The choice and description of this anonymization process will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

- *For Primary and secondary data collected via Twitter*

The Twitter data collector application downloads any related tweets periodically and provides them as input to the Advanced Data Analytics Engine (ADME) for the Unstructured Data module. The data retrieved are the date and time the tweet has been posted, the tweet’s text, the tweet ID, the number of retweets and likes, and the tweet’s location. All other information is discarded. The ADME for Unstructured Data module uses the information provided by the Twitter data collector application as input, aiming to process the tweet’s text and derive the overall emotion of the tweets, their geographic distribution, topics identified, and the context of the discussion (most popular hashtags and mentions, topics people are tweeting about, entities identified in text, such as people, locations, organizations etc.). After having retrieved the above information, the tweets are deleted. The only information being kept is the aggregated results from the analysis performed above (perceptions, context of discussion, geographic distribution).

At this stage of the project, the anonymization techniques currently being envisaged by ICCS are generalization, data masking and data substitution. The choice and description of the anonymization process will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

- *For Statistical secondary data collected from Border crossing points (end-user organizations)*

At this stage of the project, the consortium is verifying with the end-user organizations (MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS, CYPOL) whether the statistical data of Secondary data collected from border crossing points are available and can be shared with the METICOS joint controllers.

Once the availability of the end-users' data will be confirmed and in order to ensure that the anonymization processes will be carried out effectively by the end-user organizations before that the information is transmitted to the METICOS platform, it is planned to organize a workshop with MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS and CYPOL. This workshop will be dedicated to discuss the anonymization techniques being applied in order to avoid risks of re-identification. These anonymization techniques will be detailed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

4.3 Requirements for social sensing source

After a thorough search about which social media platform is most appropriate for data collection and data processing in order to understand user's/traveller's acceptance in BCPs, we concluded that the most valuable social sensing tool for the METICOS project is **Twitter**. The benefits of using Twitter in comparison to that of Facebook are presented below:

- In comparison to other social media platforms, the Twitter API is more open and accessible. This makes Twitter more appealing to developers creating tools to access data. In comparison, Facebook data are challenging to obtain and are only available on an aggregate level for marketing purposes.
- Because Twitter offers a search feature that allows users to look up tweets, and tweets also appear within Google search results, it's easier to find and follow conversations. On the other hand, Facebook is considered more of a private platform and not all public posts appear in Google Search results.
- When it comes to data collection, because Twitter has a strong hashtag culture, this makes it easier for gathering, sorting, and extending searches. Although Facebook offers hashtag capability, the use of hashtags does not appear to be as widespread as it is on Twitter.
- Twitter creates an automatic database of information in real-time, which means that as it is archived, it will become a unique source of historical information.

4.4 Requirements of the agent-based simulation tool

The requirements for the agent-based simulation tool that will be used for the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit are as follows:

- to allow the use of visual modelling languages, scripting, and extensibility
- to ease the development process
- to be open-source
- to extend default models with Java
- to allow all types of simulations (Discrete/Continuous, Micro/Macro Level)
- to have a broad spectrum of capabilities – including multi-agents models
- to keep the model building process simple and clear

According to these requirements and after an exploration of the availability as well as the needs that the toolkit is called to address, **AnyLogic** tool has been selected and will be applied for the purposes of the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit. Specifically, it is the only object-oriented M&S (Modelling and Simulation) software that supports ABM techniques with prebuilt extendible and graphical libraries, as

well as access to all Java API that enables for adding any specific functionality. Also, it is freely available at no cost, open-source and it is used easily compared to other agent-based simulation tools. Furthermore, AnyLogic is currently the most appropriate M&S tool for modelling in a modular, hierarchical, and incremental way, allowing systems to be represented to any level of detail.

AnyLogic Simulation in METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit

To start with simulating passengers’ behaviour while entering and using the BCP technologies, a basic BCP will be designed (Figure 9). Firstly, “passenger agents” will be called the different passengers entering the airport/seaport/landborder. Several parameters would be defined for each passenger, such as age, gender, education, country, experience, etc. Other external parameters might also affect their overall behavioural pattern, such as location, time, etc.

For these parameters, random values will be generated for each of the “passenger agent” entities while they are entering the area. Synthetic data from the simulations will be created by collecting these values from simulations in order to use them for making technology acceptance decisions. Also, several initial rules will be created in order to define the technology acceptance in smart border control technologies for the passenger. A first simulation flow created with AnyLogic is given in Figure 9.

Finally, after getting the random values for different parameters for the passenger agent, they will be evaluated with the rules defined previously. In this way, the technology acceptance in the simulation will be shown if the passenger is either happy, very happy, sad, fearful or confused.

Figure 9 A first simulation flow

4.5 Identification of social sensing techniques to be used for the social sensing toolkit

WP6 focuses on Social Sensing Toolkit that correlates collected data from different sources (e.g. social media, websites, questionnaires etc.) in order to validate the technology acceptance and to monitor the social acceptance considering the different behavioural patterns of the people and the interactions between them trying to pass the EU border control systems. Such a platform may be used by border authorities in order to correlate and analyze different data collected for more effective and efficient Border management and to better detect and understand how the EU is perceived in countries abroad and how this may result in a security threat for the EU.

Agent-based simulation combines a theory-informed and data-driven examination of complex interaction processes, thus highly relevant in addressing the problem of adopting new technologies in BCPs. Also, by TAM, some aspects can be covered such as: 1) user characteristics like travel habits, technology awareness/attitudes, 2) cultural background, 3) expected ease of use, 4) performance expectancy etc. Furthermore, due to the general lack of TAM datasets matching the targeted technologies and application context, the main source of METICOS TAM modelling data will result from the data collection activities (such as interviews, social media feedback, questionnaires etc.) performed within the project. So, we conclude in discussing social sensing techniques as relevant for the work related to the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit, as follows: (Figure 10): 1) Data collection from different sources, 2) Agent-based simulation, and 3) Technology acceptance model (TAM)

- Data collection

As mentioned in the 4.2.1 subsection, The METICOS platform receives data originating from Primary and Secondary data sources. Primary data sources originate from: 1) Questionnaires, 2) METICOS Mobile Application, 3) METICOS Tablet Application, and 4) Twitter. Secondary data sources originate from: 1) Twitter, 2) Blogs/Websites and 3) Data from border crossing points.

Table 5 describes the categories of data being collected by each METICOS data source.

Table 5 Primary & Secondary data collected by different sources

Category of data source	Data source	Data being collected
Primary Data	Questionnaires	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travellers' demographics & profile • Staff member demographics & profile • Likert Scale • Structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes • Unstructured data in form of free text questions
Primary Data	METICOS Mobile Application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to cross the border • Travellers' demographics & profile • Staff member demographics & profile • Smiley face • Structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes • Unstructured data in form of free text questions
Primary Data	METICOS Tablet Application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travellers' demographics & profile • Staff member demographics & profile • Smiley face • Structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unstructured data in form of free text questions
Primary Data	Twitter	Tweet after completing use case METICOS pilot
Secondary Data	Twitter	Tweets regarding acceptance of Border Control Technologies
Secondary Data	Blogs/Websites	Online reviews of BCPs
Secondary Data	Data from border crossing points and/or SBC technologies requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Checked passengers per flight/day • Waiting Time - using SBC technologies (average per passenger/per hour) • Waiting Time - manual control (average per passenger/per hour) • Queue length - using SBC technologies (average per passenger/ per hour) • Queue length - manual control (average per passenger/ per hour) • Number of passengers controlled by Border Guard (per month/per hour) • Number of passengers who used ABC technologies (per month/per hour) • Passenger Demographics & Profiles • Recurring travellers per origin/destination • Historical passenger data • Number of access attempts with documents not accepted by the system - For BCP technologies • Number of access attempts with non-eligible documents - For BCP technologies • Number of access attempts with valid e-passport but biometric verification error - For BCP technologies • Number of complaints regarding SBC technologies (by date) • Downtime of system per month/year - For BCP technologies • FAR / FRR - For BCP technologies • Total verification time - For BCP technologies • Total access time - For BCP technologies • Total time of biometric and document verification - For BCP technologies

Additional information and details about the description of the data that will be collected can be found in D3.1. It needs to be noted that the data categories shown in this deliverable are subject to update in accordance with the progress in WP6 and other WPs. The privacy and data protection aspects, including data anonymization related to the presented data, will be considered in accordance with the guidelines given in WP3.

- Agent-based simulation

Simulation is a method that combines theory-informed and data-driven exploration of complex interaction processes, thus highly relevant in addressing the problem of adopting new technologies in

BCP within non-EU countries. A multi-agent-based simulation engine will be implemented in order to monitor the social acceptance considering the different behavioural patterns of the people and the interactions between them trying to pass the EU border control systems. Since the final objective would be to evolve towards a safe and effective no gate solution, the simulation tool will go towards achieving this final state and provide related outcomes. The simulation phase allows the imitation of typical individuals with given sets of attributes' values on one side against a specific BCP technology with given attributes on the other side, within a given country or system, as part of a possible scenario.

Additionally, some rules will be needed in order to define the technology acceptance level/rate for one set of agents (e.g. SBCTs) as compared to another set of agents (e.g. travellers, border staff). These rules will be defined using synthetic data, data from pilots and data from the social sensing stage.

- Technology acceptance model (TAM)

Existing technology acceptance models (TAM) will be evaluated and extended with additional security and privacy-related aspects to provide evaluated and appropriate models, which will be used to assess border control scenarios from a user perspective. There is a connection between the TAM and social sensing toolkit since, from one viewpoint, the social sensing toolkit will offer some of the data that is needed for TAM in order to make technology acceptance decisions, and on the other hand, rules that come from pilot partners and social sensing will be required for the development and implementation of the TAM. Specifically, for WP6, once the data categories required for the social sensing toolkit will be identified (Figure 7), there will be a chance to compare the technology acceptance decision by TAM and technology acceptance prediction by the social sensing toolkit, simultaneously. So, in this way, there will be the chance to show the technology acceptance of BCPs in a more consolidated manner.

Figure 10 Sensing Techniques for the Social Sensing Toolkit

5 Challenges and open issues

In this section, privacy and data protection challenges surrounding the actual and proposed use of data and social sensing within the METICOS project are discussed.

5.1 Privacy and data protection challenges for social sensing toolkit

As discussed above, METICOS' social sensing toolkit increases the tendency to collect, use and process sensitive personal data (e.g., alphanumeric data and social media data). Thus, the toolkit raises serious legal and policy concerns. A misuse of data, compromising the privacy of individuals or/and authorized processing of data may be irreversible and could have severe and consequences on the individual's fundamental rights.

The key issue is related to individual rights, such as respect for personal privacy¹²⁶. Personal data protection and confidentiality is also an issue, especially when personal data is stored in centralized databases [104]. People have the right to choose to what extent and how to engage with the systems and devices (e.g., data collected from sensors and social media). The METICOS' social sensing toolkit will also probably increase the risk of available information misuse as a result of unethical and/or illegal practices if sensitive traveller data and privacy are not protected adequately.

Individual acceptance of METICOS' social sensing toolkit should be actively promoted through ensuring transparency of decision-making, clear policy regarding the purpose of social sensing toolkit and how it is used, as well as increased measures dedicated to preserving personal rights and personal data protection. Since greater use of personal data impacts upon human rights, there needs to be an honest and assertive study of what the risks are to personal rights and privacy as well as how these risks are mitigated.

For this reason, WP3 aims to identify and address the ethical and privacy implications of the METICOS platform to ensure that METICOS project is in compliance with fundamental human rights legislation as well as privacy and data protection legislation. In Deliverable D3.1 (Impact assessment and recommendations), the privacy impact assessment process is conducted to consider the privacy and data protection issues and impacts posed by the METICOS project to identify privacy risks and propose/plan the appropriate mitigation solutions. Moreover, Deliverable D3.3 seeks to assess the risk to human rights to prevent METICOS components from breaching fundamental rights and contributing to re-creating gender discrimination and/or negatively impacting socio-cultural factors. Refer to WP1 Deliverables for more details about the ethical guidelines and WP3 for impact assessment.

5.2 Privacy and data protection

In order to ensure respect for data protection and privacy, the following points present the aspects of data protection that relate most directly to METICOS' social sensing toolkit data processing. There are many factors to consider when it comes to data protection for METICOS' social sensing toolkit, such as (among others):

- **Compliance:** The social sensing toolkit and its use must respect the core fundamental rights of humanity, impartiality and independence. Moreover, the social sensing toolkit needs to

¹²⁶ S. Zeadally and M. Badra, *Privacy in a Digital, Networked World: Technologies, Implications and Solutions*. Springer, 2015.

respect the principle of non-discrimination in providing METICOS services to different groups or individuals, based on race, colour, sex, age, language, religion, social origin, birth, disability, health, sexual orientation, etc.

- **Transparency and consent:** METICOS' data controller(s) should inform the data subjects in a transparent manner regarding the social sensing toolkit process, what data social sensing toolkit is collecting/processing and for what purposes, as well as data operations, to be performed on their personal data. Moreover, consent of users (participants) should be collected by an appropriate method enabling a freely given specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes, ensuring that individuals are fully aware that they give their consent. The data subject should be allowed to withdraw his/her consent wherever needed.
- **Compliance with security requirements:** Security requirements deal with security issues, such as confidentiality, integrity and availability when collecting personal related data. METICOS' data controller(s) ensures data confidentiality, verifiability and availability to guarantee data security and to prevent risks emerging from the loss and theft of the technology/data. Data must be protected both logically (such as to prevent data unauthorized access from hacking or other external threats) and physically (such as data loss, such as the irreversible failure of a storage device).

Additional information on the METICOS information sheet, consent form and guidelines on how to ensure compliance with privacy and data protection regulations are available under the activities and work described in WP1 & WP3 Deliverables.

6 Conclusions and Implications for the METICOS Project

This deliverable has provided an overview of the state of the art that is relevant for the functional and operational requirements for the Social Sensing Platform, including methodologies for the description and structuring of the Platform of WP6 of the METICOS project as well as the requirements for social sensing sources and agent-based simulation tools that will be used at Social Sensing Platform. In Section 3, a more general overview of the smart border control technologies (SBCTs) was given as well as a SOTA in-based simulation (application domain and tools) and social sensing (applications, social sensing media sources). To this end, it includes an overview of technology acceptance, highlighting the relation between technology acceptance and border control technologies.

Section 4 includes a survey and SOTA from possible social sources that will be used for METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit. Specifically, it provides the proposed architecture for developing the METICOS social sensing toolkit as well as identification of required data categories and data types for the social sensing toolkit, followed by a data collection template. In addition, in this section, requirements for social sensing source and agent-based simulation tool are analysed, followed by social sensing techniques that will be used for the social sensing toolkit. This task (T6.1) will provide useful information for the upcoming work in the METICOS:

The proposed architecture for developing the METICOS social sensing toolkit is divided into two stages: 1) agent-based modelling and simulation and 2) social sensing.

Stage 1 (Agent-based simulation) development:

- Synthetic data will be created for the relevant data attributes and data types and manual rules in order to create initial simulations reflecting the traveller's as well as border staff's interaction and technology acceptance for border control technologies.
- The synthetic data and manual rules will be updated with the data from the pilots to include real scenarios and actual technology acceptance rules.

Stage 2 (Social sensing) development:

- The information from other sources like online social networks, the web, BCPs to further enhance the learning of the agent-based simulation engine will be used.
- WP5 will give additional information as it is also related to technology acceptance decisions, as social sensing will serve as a validation part for the engine in order to assess its accuracy for predicting technology acceptance.

Agent-based simulation tool for METICOS social sensing toolkit:

According to the functional requirements for the most appropriate agent-based simulation tool, **AnyLogic tool** has been selected for the purposes of the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit due to the next reasons:

- AnyLogic is the only object-oriented M&S (Modelling and Simulation) software that supports ABM techniques with prebuilt extendible and graphical libraries, as well as access to all Java API that enables for adding any specific functionality.

- AnyLogic is freely available at no cost, open-source and it is used easily compared to other agent-based simulation tools.
- AnyLogic is currently the most appropriate M&S tool for modelling in a modular, hierarchical, and incremental way, allowing systems to be represented to any level of detail.

Social sensing source for METICOS social sensing toolkit:

According to the functional requirements for the most appropriate social sensing media source, **Twitter** has been selected for the purposes of the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit due to the next reasons:

- In comparison to other social media platforms, the Twitter API is more open and accessible, making Twitter more appealing for creating tools to access data.
- Data from other social media platforms (Facebook, LinkedIn) are extremely difficult to obtain and are only available on an aggregate level for marketing purposes.
- When it comes to data collection, because Twitter has a strong hashtag culture, this makes it easier for gathering, sorting, and extending searches.
- Twitter creates an automatic database of information in real-time, which means that as it is archived, it will become a unique source of historical information.
- Twitter offers a search feature that allows users to look up tweets, and tweets also appear within Google search results; it is easier to find and follow conversations.

Datasets & Data Collection:

- The social sensing toolkit will use the information from the questionnaires activities of WP5 to collect technology acceptance related data and rules.
- The social sensing toolkit will give input to the WP5 for making technology acceptance decisions. Further details about this will be discussed in D6.2 and D6.3.
- The collection of all datasets that will be used within METICOS platform is likely to provide further synergies to WP7 with regard to developing data management mechanisms, ensuring a high level of data quality and accessibility for the big data analytics applications.
- In addition, the definition of datasets of this deliverable will help T7.2 in order to create and develop data models for effectively representing vast volumes of heterogeneous data obtained from the data storage and filtering algorithms described in the previous task (T7.1).
- The collection of all datasets that will be used within METICOS platform is likely to provide further synergies to WP8 with regard to developing the Back-End of the METICOS software infrastructure based on a collaborative private Cloud platform where all the data exchanged and managed by the METICOS components will be residing.

This deliverable presents METICOS' embedded functional and operational requirements for the METICOS Social Sensing Platform. In addition, the procedures that can be monitored for structuring the Platform, will be included in the relevant upcoming deliverables, D.6.2. "Social Data analysis and extracted perceptions" and D6.3. "METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit".

7 Bibliography

- SIJIACHEN, S. (2022). Effects of Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) on Civil Aviation: Economic Impact Analysis. Retrieved 14 July 2022, from https://www.icao.int/sustainability/Documents/Covid-19/ICAO_coronavirus_Econ_Impact.pdf
- “1. Creating agent types | AnyLogic Help.” <https://anylogic.help/tutorials/turbine-maintenance/1-different-types-of-agents.html> (accessed Jun. 22, 2021).
- “Aruba Happy Flow lays foundations for European preclearance,” *Future Travel Experience*, Jun. 04, 2015. <https://www.futuretravelexperience.com/2015/06/aruba-happy-flow-lays-foundations-for-european-precleanance/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).
- “Australia to introduce next generation Automated Border Control eGates,” *PASSENGER SELF SERVICE*, Jul. 27, 2017. <https://www.passengerselfservice.com/2017/07/australia-to-introduce-next-generation-automated-border-control-egates/> (accessed Aug. 02, 2021).
- “Bancomzvjazok.” <https://www.bkc.com.ua/en/direction-cordon/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).
- “BorderXpress™ – Innovative Travel Solutions.” <https://www.innovativetravelsolutions.ca/products/borderxpress/> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).
- “EasyPASS - EasyPASS-RTP.” https://www.easypass.de/EasyPass/EN/EasyPASS-RTP/rtp_node.html (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).
- “EasyPASS,” *U.S. Customs and Border Protection*. <https://www.cbp.gov/global-entry/other-programs/easypass> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).
- “Features.” <https://www.anylogic.com/features/> (accessed Jun. 11, 2021).
- “Information and communication technology (ICT) - Internet access - OECD Data,” *theOECD*. <http://data.oecd.org/ict/internet-access.htm> (accessed Aug. 02, 2021).
- “Video: Just walk through a tunnel for Dubai Airports passport control | Transport – Gulf News.” <https://gulfnews.com/uae/transport/video-just-walk-through-a-tunnel-for-dubai-airports-passport-control-1.69728701> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).
- “Vision-Box’s Happy Flow™ Inaugurated at Aruba Airport | Vision-Box is the leading provider of electronic identity management solutions, improving efficiency and security in gov, travel, border control and more.” <https://www.vision-box.com/pressroom/press-releases/vision-boxes-happy-flow-inaugurated-at-aruba-airport> (accessed Aug. 04, 2021).
- A. C. Charania, J. R. Olds, and D. DePasquale, “Sub-orbital space tourism: Predictions of the future marketplace using agent-based modeling,” in *Proceedings of the 57th International Astronautical Congress (AIAA), Valencia, Spain, 2006*, pp. 2–6.
- A. Djanatliev, R. German, P. Kolominsky-Rabas, and B. M. Hofmann, “Hybrid simulation with loosely coupled system dynamics and agent-based models for prospective health technology assessments,” in *Proceedings of the 2012 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC), 2012*, pp. 1–12.
- A. Kumar, A. Sharma, and A. Arora, “Anxious depression prediction in real-time social data,” 2019.
- A. Madan, M. Cebrian, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, “Social sensing for epidemiological behavior change,” in *Proceedings of the 12th ACM international conference on Ubiquitous computing, 2010*, pp. 291–300.
- A. Madan, S. T. Moturu, D. Lazer, and A. Pentland, “Social sensing: obesity, unhealthy eating and exercise in face-to-face networks,” in *Wireless Health 2010, 2010*, pp. 104–110.
- A. Pellegrini et al., “Simulation-Based Evolutionary Optimization of Air Traffic Management,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8. pp. 161551–161570, 2020. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3021192.
- A. Taneja, A. Wang, and M. K. Raja, “Assessing the impact of concern for privacy and innovation characteristics in the adoption of biometric technologies,” 2006.
- A.-M. Oostveen, M. Kaufmann, E. Krempel, and G. Grasemann, “Automated border control: a comparative usability study at two European airports,” 2014.
- B. Custers and H. Uršič, “Big data and data reuse: a taxonomy of data reuse for balancing big data benefits and personal data protection,” *Int. Data Priv. Law*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 4–15, 2016.

- B. Nyagadza, "Search engine marketing and social media marketing predictive trends," *J. Digit. Media Policy*, 2020.
- C. C. Aggarwal and T. Abdelzaher, "Social sensing," in *Managing and mining sensor data*, Springer, 2013, pp. 237–297.
- C. Chew and G. Eysenbach, "Pandemics in the age of Twitter: content analysis of Tweets during the 2009 H1N1 outbreak," *PLoS One*, vol. 5, no. 11, p. e14118, 2010.
- C. L. Miltgen, A. Popovič, and T. Oliveira, "Determinants of end-user acceptance of biometrics: Integrating the 'Big 3' of technology acceptance with privacy context," *Decis. Support Syst.*, vol. 56, pp. 103–114, 2013.
- C. W. Reynolds, "Flocks, herds and schools: A distributed behavioral model," in *Proceedings of the 14th annual conference on Computer graphics and interactive techniques*, 1987, pp. 25–34.
- D. Grether, S. Fürbas, and K. Nagel, "Agent-based modelling and simulation of air transport technology," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 19, pp. 821–828, 2013.
- D. H. Lee and P. Brusilovsky, "Using self-defined group activities for improving recommendations in collaborative tagging systems," in *Proceedings of the fourth ACM conference on Recommender systems*, 2010, pp. 221–224.
- D. P. Jones, *Biomedical sensors*. Momentum press, 2010.
- D. S. Leberherz, F. Lorig, and I. J. Timm, "Agent-based modeling and simulation of individual elderly care decision-making," in 2018 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC), 2018, pp. 1025–1036.
- D. S. Utomo, B. S. Onggo, and S. Eldridge, "Applications of agent-based modelling and simulation in the agri-food supply chains," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 269, no. 3, pp. 794–805, 2018.
- D. Wang, B. K. Szymanski, T. Abdelzaher, H. Ji, and L. Kaplan, "The age of social sensing," *Computer*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 36–45, 2019.
- D. Wang, T. Abdelzaher, and L. Kaplan, *Social sensing: building reliable systems on unreliable data*. Morgan Kaufmann, 2015.
- E. Bonabeau, "Agent-based modeling: Methods and techniques for simulating human systems," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 99, no. suppl 3, pp. 7280–7287, 2002.
- E. D'Andrea, P. Ducange, B. Lazzerini, and F. Marcelloni, "Real-time detection of traffic from twitter stream analysis," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 2269–2283, 2015.
- F. D. Davis, R. P. Bagozzi, and P. R. Warshaw, "User acceptance of computer technology: A comparison of two theoretical models," *Manag. Sci.*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 982–1003, 1989.
- G. Pirelli, "Usability in public services and border control," in *Symposium of the Austrian HCI and Usability Engineering Group*, 2009, pp. 532–552.
- G. Sakellari and G. Loukas, "A survey of mathematical models, simulation approaches and testbeds used for research in cloud computing," *Simul. Model. Pract. Theory*, vol. 39, pp. 92–103, 2013.
- H. Kopka and W. Patrick, *DALY, A Guide to LaTeX*. Addison-Wesley, 1999.
- I. Capezzuto *et al.*, "An app based air quality social sensing system built on open source Hw/Sw tools," in *Sensors*, Springer, 2015, pp. 309–313.
- J. An and I. Weber, "Whom should we sense in 'social sensing'-analyzing which users work best for social media now-casting," *EPJ Data Sci.*, vol. 4, pp. 1–22, 2015.
- J. B. Kennedy, "Plato's Forms, Pythagorean Mathematics, and Stochometry," *Apeiron*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 1–32, 2010.
- J. Fraden, *Handbook of modern sensors*, vol. 3. Springer, 2010.
- J. Lifton, M. Feldmeier, Y. Ono, C. Lewis, and J. A. Paradiso, "A platform for ubiquitous sensor deployment in occupational and domestic environments," in *Proceedings of the 6th international conference on Information processing in sensor networks*, 2007, pp. 119–127.
- K. Gupta, R. Beri, V. Behal, K. Gupta, R. Beri, and V. Behal, "Cloud computing: a survey on cloud simulation tools," *Int. J. Innov. Res. Sci. Technol. IJRST*, vol. 2, no. 11, 2016.
- K. Martins-Turner, K. Nagel, and M. Zilske, "Agent-based modelling and simulation of tour planning in urban freight traffic," 2019.

- L. Backstrom, J. Kleinberg, L. Lee, and C. Danescu-Niculescu-Mizil, "Characterizing and curating conversation threads: expansion, focus, volume, re-entry," in *Proceedings of the sixth ACM international conference on Web search and data mining*, 2013, pp. 13–22.
- L. Chen, J. Hoey, C. D. Nugent, D. J. Cook, and Z. Yu, "Sensor-based activity recognition," *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern. Part C Appl. Rev.*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 790–808, 2012.
- L. Isella *et al.*, "Close encounters in a pediatric ward: measuring face-to-face proximity and mixing patterns with wearable sensors," *PloS One*, vol. 6, no. 2, p. e17144, 2011.
- L. Kou, W. H. Fan, and S. Song, "Multi-agent-based modelling and simulation of high-speed train," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 86, p. 12, 2020. doi: 10.1016/j.compeleceng.2020.106744.
- L. Zhang, G. Landucci, G. Reniers, F. Ovidi, N. Khakzad, and J. Zhou, "Applying agent based modelling and simulation for domino effect assessment in the chemical industries," *Chem. Eng.*, vol. 67, 2018.
- M. Atzmueller and K. Hilgenberg, "Towards capturing social interactions with sdcf: An extensible framework for mobile sensing and ubiquitous data collection," in *Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Modeling Social Media*, 2013, pp. 1–4.
- M. Atzmueller, M. Becker, and J. Mueller, "Collective sensing platforms," in *Participatory Sensing, Opinions and Collective Awareness*, Springer, 2017, pp. 115–133.
- M. Avvenuti, S. Cresci, A. Marchetti, C. Meletti, and M. Tesconi, "Predictability or early warning: using social media in modern emergency response," *IEEE Internet Comput.*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 4–6, 2016.
- M. EL-GOHARY, O. TOLBA, and A. EL-ANTABLI, "AGENT-BASED MODELING AND SIMULATION FOR FOOD COURT SEATING DESIGN," *J. Eng. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 771–788, 2020.
- M. Herrera, M. Pérez-Hernández, A. Kumar Parlikad, and J. Izquierdo, "Multi-agent systems and complex networks: Review and applications in systems engineering," *Processes*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 312, 2020.
- M. Kessentini, N. B. B. Saoud, and S. Sboui, "Agent-Based Modeling and Simulation of Inventory Disruption Management in Supply Chain," in *2018 International Conference on High Performance Computing & Simulation (HPCS)*, 2018, pp. 1008–1014.
- M. Kibanov, G. Stumme, I. Amin, and J. G. Lee, "Mining social media to inform peatland fire and haze disaster management," *Soc. Netw. Anal. Min.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–19, 2017.
- M. Klein, U. J. Frey, and M. Reeg, "Models Within Models–Agent-Based Modelling and Simulation in Energy Systems Analysis," *J. Artif. Soc. Soc. Simul.*, vol. 22, no. 4, 2019.
- M. Laibowitz, N.-W. Gong, and J. A. Paradiso, "Wearable sensing for dynamic management of dense ubiquitous media," in *2009 Sixth International Workshop on Wearable and Implantable Body Sensor Networks*, 2009, pp. 3–8.
- M. Pardo and W. F. Coronado, "Agent-based modeling and simulation to adoption process of information technologies in health systems," *IEEE Lat. Am. Trans.*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 3358–3363, 2016.
- M. Salathe *et al.*, "Digital epidemiology," *PLoS Comput Biol*, vol. 8, no. 7, p. e1002616, 2012.
- M. Scott, T. Acton, and M. Hughes, "An assessment of biometric identities as a standard for e-government services," *Int. J. Serv. Stand.*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 271–286, 2005.
- M. T. Rashid, D. Y. Zhang, and D. Wang, "Socialdrone: An integrated social media and drone sensing system for reliable disaster response," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2020-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*, 2020, pp. 218–227.
- M. Taboada, E. Cabrera, F. Epelde, M. L. Iglesias, and E. Luque, "Using an agent-based simulation for predicting the effects of patients derivation policies in emergency departments," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 18, pp. 641–650, 2013.
- M. Ylikaupila, S. Toivonen, M. Kulju, and M. Jokela, "Understanding the factors affecting UX and technology acceptance in the context of automated border controls," in *2014 IEEE Joint Intelligence and Security Informatics Conference*, 2014, pp. 168–175.

- N. Eagle and A. S. Pentland, "Reality mining: sensing complex social systems," *Pers. Ubiquitous Comput.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 255–268, 2006.
- N. Gilbert and S. Bankes, "Platforms and methods for agent-based modeling," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 99, no. suppl 3, pp. 7197–7198, 2002.
- N. Giordano, S. Rosati, F. Valeri, A. Borchiellini, and G. Balestra, "Agent-Based Modeling and Simulation of Care Delivery for Patients with Thrombotic and Bleeding Disorders.," in *MIE, 2020*, pp. 1193–1194.
- N. Malleon, "Using agent-based models to simulate crime," in *Agent-based models of geographical systems*, Springer, 2012, pp. 411–434.
- N. YACHOU and R. Aboulaich, "Agent Based Modeling and Simulation for Home Financing. Application in Netlogo Platform.," *J. Appl. Econ. Sci.*, vol. 13, no. 3, 2018.
- P. Caillou and M. Sebag, "Pride and prejudice on a centralized academic labor market," in *Artificial economics*, Springer, 2009, pp. 29–40.
- P. Ducange and M. Fazzolari, "Social sensing and sentiment analysis: Using social media as useful information source," in *2017 International Conference on Smart Systems and Technologies (SST)*, 2017, pp. 301–306.
- Q. Zheng and S. Lei, "An agent-based experimental model for innovative talent management in universities," in *2010 International Conference on Electronics and Information Engineering*, 2010, vol. 1, pp. V1-552-V1-556.
- R. Axelrod, *The complexity of cooperation: Agent-based models of competition and collaboration*, vol. 3. Princeton university press, 1997.
- R. B. Matthews, N. G. Gilbert, A. Roach, J. G. Polhill, and N. M. Gotts, "Agent-based land-use models: a review of applications," *Landsc. Ecol.*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 1447–1459, 2007.
- R. Buyya, A. Beloglazov, and J. Abawajy, "Energy-efficient management of data center resources for cloud computing: a vision, architectural elements, and open challenges," *ArXiv Prepr. ArXiv10060308*, 2010.
- R. Buyya, R. Ranjan, and R. N. Calheiros, "Modeling and simulation of scalable Cloud computing environments and the CloudSim toolkit: Challenges and opportunities," in *2009 international conference on high performance computing & simulation*, 2009, pp. 1–11.
- R. Mayer, H. Gupta, E. Saurez, and U. Ramachandran, "The fog makes sense: Enabling social sensing services with limited internet connectivity," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Social Sensing*, 2017, pp. 61–66.
- R. N. Calheiros, R. Ranjan, A. Beloglazov, C. A. De Rose, and R. Buyya, "CloudSim: a toolkit for modeling and simulation of cloud computing environments and evaluation of resource provisioning algorithms," *Softw. Pract. Exp.*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 23–50, 2011.
- R. P. Bagozzi, F. D. Davis, and P. R. Warshaw, "Development and test of a theory of technological learning and usage," *Hum. Relat.*, vol. 45, no. 7, pp. 659–686, 1992.
- R. Tobias and C. Hofmann, "Evaluation of free Java-libraries for social-scientific agent based simulation," *J. Artif. Soc. Soc. Simul.*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. online, 2004.
- S. A. Golder and M. W. Macy, "Digital footprints: Opportunities and challenges for online social research," *Annu. Rev. Sociol.*, vol. 40, pp. 129–152, 2014.
- S. A. Shaikh and J. R. Rabaiotti, "Characteristic trade-offs in designing large-scale biometric-based identity management systems," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 342–351, 2010.
- S. Abar, G. K. Theodoropoulos, P. Lemarinier, and G. M. O'Hare, "Agent Based Modelling and Simulation tools: A review of the state-of-art software," *Comput. Sci. Rev.*, vol. 24, pp. 13–33, 2017.
- S. Bandini, S. Manzoni, and G. Vizzari, "Agent based modeling and simulation: an informatics perspective," *J. Artif. Soc. Soc. Simul.*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 4, 2009.
- Ş. Bora, V. Evren, S. Emek, and I. Çakırlar, "Agent-based modeling and simulation of blood vessels in the cardiovascular system," *Simulation*, vol. 95, no. 4, pp. 297–312, 2019.
- S. Bouarfa, H. A. Blom, and R. Curran, "Agent-based modeling and simulation of coordination by airline operations control," *IEEE Trans. Emerg. Top. Comput.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 9–20, 2016.

- S. Čavoški and A. Marković, "Agent-based modelling and simulation in the analysis of customer behaviour on B2C e-commerce sites," *J. Simul.*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 335–345, 2017.
- S. Dabirian, M. Khanzadi, and M. Moussazadeh, "Predicting labor costs in construction projects using agent-based modeling and simulation," *Sci. Iran.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 91–101, 2016.
- S. F. Harbo, S. Zaferanlouei, and M. Korpås, "Agent based modelling and simulation of plug-in electric vehicles adoption in norway," in *2018 Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC)*, 2018, pp. 1–7.
- S. F. Railsback and V. Grimm, *Agent-based and individual-based modeling: a practical introduction*. Princeton university press, 2019.
- S. Nasir, M. Asif, and S. Ullah, "An Agent Based Model for Diffusion of Smart Grid Technology in the Society," in *2018 14th International Conference on Emerging Technologies (ICET)*, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- S. Rizwana and M. Sasikumar, "Cloud Simulation Tools: A Comparative Analysis," in *International Journal of Computer Applications (0975–8887), International conference on Green Computing and Technology*, 2013, pp. 11–14.
- S. Zeadally and M. Badra, *Privacy in a Digital, Networked World: Technologies, Implications and Solutions*. Springer, 2015.
- T. Li, L. Liang, Z. Zili, L. Hong, and X. Fuyuan, "Multi-Agent Based Modelling and Simulation for Understanding Tempo-Spatial Patterns of Surgery Wait Times," *J. Syst. Simul.*, vol. 29, no. 5, p. 979, 2017.
- V. I. Sergeyev and N. N. Lychkina, "Agent-based modelling and simulation of inter-organizational integration and coordination of supply chain participants," in *2019 IEEE 21st Conference on Business Informatics (CBI)*, 2019, vol. 1, pp. 436–444.
- V. Venkatesh, M. G. Morris, G. B. Davis, and F. D. Davis, "User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view," *MIS Q.*, pp. 425–478, 2003.
- W. Peng, W. Krueger, A. Grushin, P. Carlos, V. Manikonda, and M. Santos, "Graph-based methods for the analysis of large-scale multiagent systems," in *Proceedings of The 8th International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems-Volume 1*, 2009, pp. 545–552.
- Y. Liu *et al.*, "Social sensing: A new approach to understanding our socioeconomic environments," *Ann. Assoc. Am. Geogr.*, vol. 105, no. 3, pp. 512–530, 2015.
- Z. Li, Q. Huang, and C. T. Emrich, *Introduction to social sensing and big data computing for disaster management*. Taylor & Francis, 2019.

Appendix: Links to information on different existing border control technologies

1. E-gates & Border control operations at Larnaka and Pafos airports, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://www.hermesairports.com/prepare-your-journey/fly-out/e-gates-boarding-pass-readers>)
2. The first automated border control gates in Estonia are operating, August 10, 2021 (<https://www.tallinn-airport.ee/en/news/the-first-automated-border-control-gates-in-estonia-are-operating/>)
3. Athens Airport gets Automated Passport Control Units, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://balkaneu.com/athens-airport-gets-automated-passport-control-units/>)
4. Bucharest's main airport to have automated passport control gates, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://www.romania-insider.com/bucharest-airport-automated-passport-control>)
5. Bancomzvjazok, Date accessed August 10, 2021
6. Israel brings in eGates at Ben Gurion Airport: Security Document News, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<http://www.securitydocumentworld.com/article-details/i/12119/>)
7. Aruba happy Flow, Accessed August 10, 2021 (<http://www.arubahappyflow.com/>)
8. SmartGates, Australian Border Force, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://www.abf.gov.au/entering-and-leaving-australia/smartgates/arrivals#:~:text=SmartGates%20automatically%20process%20passengers%20through>)
9. Shanghai Airport Automates Check-in with Facial Recognition, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://www.voanews.com/silicon-valley-technology/shanghai-airport-automates-check-facial-recognition>)
10. Dubai airport launches facial recognition technology to fast-track immigration process, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://gulfbusiness.com/dubai-airport-launches-facial-recognition-technology-to-fasttrack-immigration-process/>)
11. EASY PASS, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (https://www.easypass.de/EasyPass/EN/What_is_EasyPASS/home_node.html)
12. PARAFE: a new generation of smart gates for the ADP Group, Date accessed August 10, 2021 ([https://www.thalesgroup.com/en/markets/digital-identity-and-security/government/customer-cases/smart-gates-paris#:~:text=The%20automated%20PARAFE%20system%20\(Automated,generation%20automated%20control%20smart%20gates\).](https://www.thalesgroup.com/en/markets/digital-identity-and-security/government/customer-cases/smart-gates-paris#:~:text=The%20automated%20PARAFE%20system%20(Automated,generation%20automated%20control%20smart%20gates).))
13. Electronic Passports, AIR Portugal, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://www.flytap.com/en-us/documentation/electronic-passport>)
14. Iris ID providing biometric ID technology at Qatar's Hamad International Airport: Biometric Update, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://www.biometricupdate.com/201705/iris-id-providing-biometric-id-technology-at-qatar-s-hamad-international-airport>)
15. Heathrow installs biometric gates to improve customer experience while maintaining security standards – IFSEC Global:Security and Fire News and Resources, Date accessed August 10, 2021 (<https://www.ifsecglobal.com/access-control/heathrow-installs-biometric-gates-to-improve-customer-experience-while-maintaining-security-standards/>)
16. <https://www.secunet.com/en/first-abc-gates-at-land-border>
17. <https://www.secunet.com/en/products-consulting/ees#c8600>

18. <https://www.secunet.com/en/products-consulting/ees>
19. <https://www.bkc.com.ua/en/direction-cordon/>

